

OCTOPUS Database v.2

Database field description tables.

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The OCTOPUS v.2 database can be accessed at: <https://octopusdata.org>

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Table S1

Database field descriptions: CRN Denudation

OCTOPUSdata/ CRN Denudation/ Global, Australian, UOW & Large basins collections. Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	[S###WTS###]	S281WTS011	Unique CRN AMS measurement identifier provided as part of the compilation.
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	MQR	Original sample identifier (as published). This is not necessarily the lab code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample.
STUDYID	varchar(5):P	[S###]	S281	Unique study identifier provided as part of the compilation
CRN_SUBCMP	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for not applicable	AUS	CRN sub-compilation membership identifier ('INT' = Global collection, 'AUS' = Australian collection, 'XXL' = Large basins, 'UOW' = unpublished/ in preparation)
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	10.25900/mpr9-yn15	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[CRNSM#####]	CRNSM04447	Unique sample identifier that, first and foremost, serves database operation. CRN SMPIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated roundup(3) "Y_WGS84" AND roundup(3) "X_WGS84" AND "SIZEMIN" AND "SIZEMAX".
SITEID	text:NN	[CRNST#####]	CRNST03977a	Unique site identifier that, first and foremost, serves database operation. CRN SITEIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated roundup(3) "Y_WGS84" AND roundup(3) "X_WGS84", with running alphabetic letter(s) added.
METASITEID	text	[value]	NA	Unique metasite identifier provided as part of the compilation. Not applicable for CRN compilations

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Wollongong Coast	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	AUS TSI – Torres Strait Islands	Refers to Sahul region. Same as “CNTRY” but needed to accommodate for ‘TSI’ or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	AU-NSW PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
BASIN	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Macquarie Rivulet	Name of river basin where study site is located
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	SEN	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	SEN_14	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGLF1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Wollongong Coast	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	South East Coast (NSW)	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	SYB	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Sydney Basin	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	150.706758	WGS84 longitude of the site
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-34.577122	WGS84 latitude of the site
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data	INTP_ND	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or ‘ORIG_’, or ‘ND_’). Second part of value refers to “ELEVATION” (‘_INTP’, or ‘_ORIG’, or ‘_ND’). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999 – no data	-9999.99	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITE_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID	text:NN	[value] or ND – no data	Codilean:2021margin	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier
OAID	varchar(11):NN	[value] or	OAID-000032	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		ND – no data		
AUTHOR	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Codilean	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR	int2	[YYYY] – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2021	Year of the publication
REFID	text	[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol] or Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	Earth-Sci_Rev_214 or second example Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e. PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/Abbrvjt.html
			Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103543	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.

Sample information

MATERIAL	varchar(6):P	[grnsizeid – value (abbreviation)]	Sa	Abbreviated type of material sampled
		1 – Sand (Sa) 2 – Silt (Si) 3 – Clay (Cl) 4 – Large boulder (LBo) 5 – Boulder (Bo) 6 – Cobble (Co) 7 – Gravel (Gr) 71 – Coarse gravel (CGr)	32 – Medium sand (MSa) 33 – Fine sand (FSa) 21 – Coarse silt (CSi) 22 – Medium silt (MSi) 23 – Fine silt (FSi) 50 – Pebble (Pe) 12 – Silty Sand (SiSa) 13 – Clayey Sand (ClSa)	15 – Mix of Sand and Boulder (SaBo) 16 – Mix of Sand and Cobble (SaCo) 17 – Mix of Sand and Gravel (SaGr) 56 – Mix of Boulders and Cobbles (BoCo) 65 – Mix of Cobbles and Boulders (CoBo) 80 – Sediment (unspecified) (Sed) 81 – Loam (Lo) 100 – Bedrock (Bed)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		72 – Medium gravel (MGr) 73 – Fine gravel (FGr) 31 – Coarse sand (CSa)	14 – Mix of Sand and Large boulder (SaLBo)	or -9999 – for no data (ND)
SIZEMIN	int2 [micron]	<i>[size in microns]</i> or 0 – no data	250	Minimum grain size sampled
SIZEMAX	int2 [micron]	<i>[size in microns]</i> or 0 – no data	500	Maximum grain size sampled
PROJEPSGID	int2	<i>[value]</i>	32755	EPSG code of projected coordinate system used for calculations
PROJECTION	varchar(13):NN	<i>[name]</i>	WGS84_UTM_44N	Human readable projected coordinate system used for calculations
AREA	numeric(12,2) [km ²]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	33.63	Basin area as calculated from projected DEM
ELEV_AVE	numeric(6,2) [m]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	388.65	Mean elevation of basin as calculated from projected DEM
ELEV_STD	numeric(6,2) [m]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	208.24	Standard deviation of elevation of basin as calculated from projected DEM
SLP_AVE	numeric [m.km ⁻¹]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	232.68	Mean slope gradient of basin as calculated from projected DEM
SLP_STD	numeric [m.km ⁻¹]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	164.26	Standard deviation of slope gradient of basin as calculated from projected DEM
SMP_DAY	int2	<i>[value]</i>	-9999	Sampling day (if published)
SMP_MONTH	int2	<i>[value]</i>	-9999	Sampling month (if published)
SMP_YEAR	int2	<i>[value]</i>	-9999	Sampling year (if published)
SMP_COMMT	text	<i>[value]</i>	-9999	Free text sample comment field.
Cosmogenic Be-10 data				
BE10NP	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	<i>[value]</i> or	90845	Published Be-10 concentration

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		23 – LLNL300 (LLNL300) 24 – LLNL300 (LLNL300-Assumed) 25 – LLNL3000 (LLNL3000) 26 – LLNL3000 (LLNL3000-Assumed)	39 – NIST_30600 (NIST_30600) 40 – NIST_30600 (NIST_30600-Assumed) 41 – NIST_Certified (NIST_Certified)	58 – NIST_30500 (NIST_30500-Assumed) or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
BECORR	numeric(5,4)	<i>[bestndid – becorr (stnd published)]</i> 1 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD) 2 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD-Assumed) 3 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD3110) 4 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD3110-Assumed) 5 – 0.9124 (BEST433) 6 – 0.9124 (BEST433-Assumed) 7 – 1.0000 (BEST433N) 8 – 1.0000 (BEST433N-Assumed) 9 – 1.0000 (ICN) 10 – 1.0000 (ICN-Assumed) 11 – 1.0000 (ICN 01-5-2) 12 – 1.0000 (ICN 01-5-2-Assumed) 13 – 1.0000 (KN01-6-2) 14 – 1.0000 (KN01-6-2-Assumed) 15 – 0.9042 (KNSTD) 16 – 0.9042 (KNSTD-Assumed) 17 – 1.0000 (KNSTD3110) 18 – 1.0000 (KNSTD3110-Assumed) 19 – 0.9313 (LLNL1000) 20 – 0.9313 (LLNL1000-Assumed) 21 – 0.9042 (LLNL10000) 22 – 0.9042 (LLNL10000-Assumed)	1.000 23 – 0.8562 (LLNL300) 24 – 0.8562 (LLNL300-Assumed) 25 – 0.8644 (LLNL3000) 26 – 0.8644 (LLNL3000-Assumed) 27 – 0.8761 (LLNL31000) 28 – 0.8761 (LLNL31000-Assumed) 29 – 1.0000 (NIST SRM-4325) 30 – 1.0000 (NIST SRM-4325-Assumed) 31 – 1.0000 (NIST_27900) 32 – 1.0000 (NIST_27900-Assumed) 33 – 0.9313 (NIST_30000) 34 – 0.9313 (NIST_30000-Assumed) 35 – 0.9251 (NIST_30200) 36 – 0.9251 (NIST_30200-Assumed) 37 – 0.9221 (NIST_30300) 38 – 0.9221 (NIST_30300-Assumed) 39 – 0.9130 (NIST_30600) 40 – 0.9130 (NIST_30600-Assumed) 41 – 1.0425 (NIST_Certified)	Correction factor for a certain standardization that, multiplied with determined Be-10 concentration, will yield a nuclide concentration that is consistent with 07KNSTD 42 – 1.0425 (NIST_Certified-Assumed) 43 – 0.9124 (S2007) 44 – 0.9124 (S2007-Assumed) 45 – 1.0000 (S2007N) 46 – 1.0000 (S2007N-Assumed) 47 – 0.9124 (S555) 48 – 0.9124 (S555-Assumed) 49 – 1.0000 (S555N) 50 – 1.0000 (S555N-Assumed) 51 – 1.0000 (SMD-Be-12) 52 – 1.0000 (SMD-Be-12-Assumed) 53 – 1.0000 (SRM KN-5-2) 54 – 1.0000 (SRM KN-5-2-Assumed) 55 – 1.0000 (STD-11) 56 – 1.0000 (STD-11-Assumed) 57 – 0.9124 (NIST_30500) 58 – 0.9124 (NIST_30500-Assumed) or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
BEAMS	text	<i>[amsid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation ANSTO (ANSTO) 2 – (ANSTO-Assumed) 3 – Australian National University ANU (ANU) 4 – (ANU-Assumed)	ANSTO 13 – Climate and Environment Sciences Laboratory LSCE, Pierre Simon Laplace Institute (Gif-sur-Yvette) 14 – (Gif-sur-Yvette-Assumed) 15 – Korea Institute of Geoscience and Mineral Resources KIGAM (KIGAM AMS)	Abbreviated name of AMS where measurements were done 22 – (MALT Tokyo AMS-Assumed) 23 – Purdue Rare Isotope Measurement Laboratory PRIME (PRIME-Lab) 24 – (PRIME-Lab-Assumed) 25 – Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre (SUERC) 26 – (SUERC-Assumed)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		5 – Centre for Research and Teaching in Environmental Geoscience CEREGE (ASTER) 6 – (ASTER-Assumed) 7 – University of Cologne (Cologne) 8 – (Cologne-Assumed) 9 – Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf HZDR (DREAMS) 10 – (DREAMS-Assumed) 11 – Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich ETH-Zurich (ETH-Zurich) 12 – (ETH-Zurich-Assumed)	16 – (KIGAM AMS-Assumed) 17 – Korea Institute of Science and Technology (KIST Seoul) 18 – (KIST Seoul-Assumed) 19 – Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory LLNL, Center for Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (LLNL-CAMS) 20 – (LLNL-CAMS-Assumed) 21 – Micro Analysis Laboratory, Tandem accelerator MALT, The University of Tokyo (MALT Tokyo AMS) 27 – Uppsala University, Tandem Laboratory (Uppsala)	28 – (Uppsala-Assumed) 29 – Compact AMS, GNS New Zealand (XCAMS (GNS)) 30 – (XCAMS (GNS)-Assumed) 31 – Xi’an AMS Center, China (XAAMS) 32 – (XAAMS-Assumed) 33 – iThemba Laboratory for Accelerator Based Sciences (iThemba LABS) 34 – (iThemba-Assumed) 35 – Tianjin University, Inst. of Surface-Earth System Sci. 36 – (Tianjin-Assumed) or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
BE10NC	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	90845	Be-10 concentration normalised to 07KNSTD
BE10NC_ERR	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	2625	Uncertainty in Be-10 concentration normalised to 07KNSTD
Denudation rate calculations using Be-10				
BEPROD	numeric [dimensionless]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	1.208	CAIRN average production scaling correction for the basin
BETOPO	numeric [dimensionless]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.988	CAIRN average topographic shielding correction for the basin
BESLFF	numeric [dimensionless]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	1.000	CAIRN average self shielding correction for the basin
BESNOW	numeric [dimensionless]	[value; three decimal places] or	1.000	CAIRN average snow shielding correction for the basin

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		-9999.99 – for no data		
BETOTS	numeric [dimensionless]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	1.193	CAIRN average combined shielding and scaling correction for the basin
EBE_GCMYR	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	[value; five decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.01054	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate in mass per unit area
ERRBE_AMS	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	[value; five decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00031	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area derived from AMS uncertainty
ERRBE_MUON	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	[value; five decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00119	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area derived from muon uncertainty
ERRBE_PROD	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	[value; five decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00212	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area derived from uncertainty in the production rate
ERRBE_TOT	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	[value; five decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00245	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area that combines all uncertainties
EBE_MMKYR	numeric [mm.kyr ⁻¹]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	39.76	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate calculated assuming density of 2650 kg.m ⁻³
EBE_ERR	numeric [mm.kyr ⁻¹]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	9.24	CAIRN Be-10 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level calculated assuming density of 2650 kg.m ⁻³
Cosmogenic Al-26 data				
AL26NP	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	[value] or	532849	Published Al-26 concentration

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		-9999 – for no data		
AL26NP_ERR	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	39946	Published 1-sigma uncertainty in Al-26 concentration
AL26EP	numeric [mm.kyr ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	50.74	Published Al-26 denudation rate
AL26EP_ERR	numeric [mm.kyr ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	12.02	Published 1-sigma uncertainty in Al-26 denudation rate
ALSTND	text:p	[alstndid – stnd used (stnd published)] 1 – ZAL94 (AL09) 2 – ZAL94 (AL09-Assumed) 3 – KNSTD (KN-4-2) 4 – KNSTD (KN-4-2-Assumed) 5 – KNSTD (KN01-X-Y) 6 – KNSTD (KN01-X-Y-Assumed) 7 – KNSTD (KNSTD) 8 – KNSTD (KNSTD-Assumed) 9 – KNSTD (KNSTD10650) 10 – KNSTD (KNSTD10650-Assumed) 11 – KNSTD (KNSTD30960) 12 – KNSTD (KNSTD30960-Assumed)	KNSTD 13 – KNSTD (NBS) 14 – KNSTD (NBS-Assumed) 15 – SMAL11 (SMAL11) 16 – SMAL11 (SMAL11-Assumed) 17 – KNSTD (Z92-0222) 18 – KNSTD (Z92-0222-Assumed) 19 – KNSTD (Z93-0221)	Name of AMS Al standardisation used. When information is not provided (would be ‘no data’), it is assumed that authors used the KNSTD standardisation as this is the most common. Standards where ‘stnd used’ == ‘KNSTD’, for the sake of simplicity, are treated as KNSTD regardless of ‘stnd published’. 20 – KNSTD (Z93-0221-Assumed) 21 – ZAL94 (ZAL94) 22 – ZAL94 (ZAL94-Assumed) 23 – ZAL94N (ZAL94N) 24 – ZAL94N (ZAL94N-Assumed) or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
ALCORR	numeric(5,4)	[alstndid – alcorr (stnd published)] 1 – 0.9134 (AL09) 2 – 0.9134 (AL09-Assumed) 3 – 1 (KN-4-2) 4 – 1 (KN-4-2-Assumed) 5 – 1 (KN01-X-Y) 6 – 1 (KN01-X-Y-Assumed) 7 – 1 (KNSTD) 8 – 1 (KNSTD-Assumed)	1.000 11 – 1 (KNSTD30960) 12 – 1 (KNSTD30960-Assumed) 13 – 1 (NBS) 14 – 1 (NBS-Assumed) 15 – 1.021 (SMAL11) 16 – 1.021 (SMAL11-Assumed)	Correction factor for a certain standardization that, multiplied with determined Al-26 concentration, will yield a nuclide concentration that is consistent with KNSTD 19 – 1 (Z93-0221) 20 – 1 (Z93-0221-Assumed) 21 – 0.9134 (ZAL94) 22 – 0.9134 (ZAL94-Assumed) 23 – 1 (ZAL94N) 24 – 1 (ZAL94N-Assumed)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		9 – 1 (KNSTD10650) 10 – 1 (KNSTD10650-Assumed)	17 – 1 (Z92-0222) 18 – 1 (Z92-0222-Assumed)	or -9999 – for no data (NA)
ALAMS	text	<i>[amsid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation ANSTO (ANSTO) 2 – (ANSTO-Assumed) 3 – Australian National University ANU (ANU) 4 – (ANU-Assumed) 5 – Centre for Research and Teaching in Environmental Geoscience CEREGE (ASTER) 6 – (ASTER-Assumed) 7 – University of Cologne (Cologne) 8 – (Cologne-Assumed) 9 – Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf HZDR (DREAMS) 10 – (DREAMS-Assumed) 11 – Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich ETH-Zurich (ETH-Zurich) 12 – (ETH-Zurich-Assumed)	ANSTO 13 – Climate and Environment Sciences Laboratory LSCE, Pierre Simon Laplace Institute (Gif-sur-Yvette) 14 – (Gif-sur-Yvette-Assumed) 15 – Korea Institute of Geoscience and Mineral Resources KIGAM (KIGAM AMS) 16 – (KIGAM AMS-Assumed) 17 – Korea Institute of Science and Technology (KIST Seoul) 18 – (KIST Seoul-Assumed) 19 – Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory LLNL, Center for Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (LLNL-CAMS) 20 – (LLNL-CAMS-Assumed) 21 – Micro Analysis Laboratory, Tandem accelerator MALT, The University of Tokyo (MALT Tokyo AMS) 27 – Uppsala University, Tandem Laboratory (Uppsala)	Abbreviated name of AMS where measurements were done 22 – (MALT Tokyo AMS-Assumed) 23 – Purdue Rare Isotope Measurement Laboratory PRIME (PRIME-Lab) 24 – (PRIME-Lab-Assumed) 25 – Scottish Universities Environmental Research Centre (SUERC) 26 – (SUERC-Assumed) 28 – (Uppsala-Assumed) 29 – Compact AMS, GNS New Zealand (XCAMS (GNS)) 30 – (XCAMS (GNS)-Assumed) 31 – Xi’an AMS Center, China (XAAMS) 32 – (XAAMS-Assumed) 33 – iThemba Laboratory for Accelerator Based Sciences (iThemba LABS) 34 – (iThemba-Assumed) 35 – Tianjin University, Inst. of Surface-Earth System Sci. 36 – (Tianjin-Assumed) or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
AL26NC	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	532849	Al-26 concentration normalised to KNSTD
AL26AP_ERR	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	39946	Uncertainty in Al-26 concentration normalised to KNSTD
Denudation rate calculations using Al-26				
ALPROD	numeric [dimensionless]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	1.208	CAIRN average production scaling correction for the basin

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
ALTOPO	numeric [dimensionless]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.988	CAIRN average topographic shielding correction for the basin
ALSELF	numeric [dimensionless]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	1.000	CAIRN average self shielding correction for the basin
ALSNOW	numeric [dimensionless]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	1.000	CAIRN average snow shielding correction for the basin
ALTOTS	numeric [dimensionless]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	1.193	CAIRN average combined shielding and scaling correction for the basin
EAL_GCMYR	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; five decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.01345	CAIRN Al-26 denudation rate in mass per unit area
ERRAL_AMS	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; five decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00105	CAIRN Al-26 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area derived from AMS uncertainty
ERRAL_MUON	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; five decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00128	CAIRN Al-26 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area derived from muon uncertainty
ERRAL_PROD	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; five decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00272	CAIRN Al-26 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area derived from uncertainty in the production rate
ERRAL_TOT	numeric [g.cm ⁻² .yr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; five decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.00319	CAIRN Al-26 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level in mass per unit area that combines all uncertainties
EAL_MMKYR	numeric [mm.kyr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	50.74	CAIRN Al-26 denudation rate calculated assuming density of 2650 kg.m ⁻³

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or -9999.99 – for no data		
EAL_ERR	numeric [mm.kyr ⁻¹]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	12.02	CAIRN AI-26 denudation rate uncertainty at 1-sigma level calculated assuming density of 2650 kg.m ⁻³

Table S2

Database field descriptions: SahulSed OSL

OCTOPUSdata/ Sahul Sedimentary Archives/ OSL collection (aeolian, fluvial, lacustrine). Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	SED_AEN_OSL#### SED_FLV_OSL#### SED_LAC_OSL####	SED_FLV_OSL0035	Unique age identifier provided as part of the sub-compilation. "OBSID1" membership → AEN (aeolian), FLV (fluvial), LAC (lacustrine); Method → OSL (Optically Stimulated Luminescence), TL (Thermoluminescence)
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	95017B	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample. Samples labelled only by numbers in the literature (e.g. 1, 2, 3 etc) have had a compound prefix – first three author name letters AND double-digit publication year – added (e.g. 'Nan87_1' for sample 1 (Nanson 1987)).
LABID	text	[value] or ND – no data	ANUOD180f	Unique lab code assigned by the lab where age was determined. For radiocarbon (and for many luminescence) labs, the first part of the lab code refers to the determining facility.
LAB_FACLT	text:P	[value]	ANU Luminescence Dating Laboratory Canberra	Name of the laboratory where age was determined (where deducible from "LABID")
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	10.25900/p5ye-rn35	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[SEDSM#####<suffix>]	SEDSM00626	Sample identifier provided as part of the compilation. SahulSed SMPIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated "X_WGS84" AND "Y_WGS84" AND "SITENAME" AND "SMPDEPTH". Re suffixes – '_pre' indicates that the matching age is preferred by the authors of the original publication; '_alt' tags alternatives to '_pre' ages; and '.o'

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
				indicates the existence of a corresponding TL ('.t') measurement on the same sample.
SITEID	text:NN	[SEDST####o.x]	SEDST0522o.a	Unique sample identifier that serves database operation. SahulSed SITEIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated "SITENAME" AND "ALTNAME1". Suffixes 'o' resp. 't' indicate OSL or TL membership, respectively, with running alphabetic letters added for ID uniqueness.
METASITEID	text	[value]	NA	Unique metasite identifier provided as part of the compilation. Not applicable for SahulSed compilations
METANAME	text	[value]	NA	Metasite name
METHODABBR	text:P:NN	[methodid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Amino Acid Racemization (AAR) 2 – Radiocarbon Dating (C14) 3 – Cation Ratio Dating (CRD) 4 – Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)	OSL 5 – Oxidisable Carbon Ratio (OCR) 6 – Optically Stimulated Lum. (OSL) 7 – Thermoluminescence (TL) 8 – Uranium-Series (U)	Abbreviated type of method used in age determination 9 – Closed-system U-Series and ESR model (CSU-ESR) 10 – Stratigraphic correlation (Strat) 11 – Coupled U-ESR model (U-ESR)
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value] or ND – no data	ND	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	AUS TSI – Torres Strait Islands	Refers to Sahul region. Same as "CNTRY" but needed to accommodate for 'TSI' or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia	AU-NT PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
LAKE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of lake where study site is located
BASIN	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Victoria River-Wiso	Name of river basin where study site is located

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS_10	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGFL1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Victoria River-Wiso	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Tanami-Timor Sea Coast	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	GSD	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Great Sandy Desert	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	132.579167	WGS84 longitude of the site
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-22.822222	WGS84 latitude of the site
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description	ORIG_INTP	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data		'ORIG_', or 'ND_'. Second part of value refers to "ELEVATION" ('_INTP', or '_ORIG', or '_ND'). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value] or -9999 – no data	570	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITENAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Napperby Creek	Name of the site
SITE_SPEC	text	[value] or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text field that allows for a brief description of the site
ALTNAME1	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	Lake Lewis	First alternative or additional name of the site (e.g., published under previous name etc.)
ALTNAME2	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Second alternative or additional name of the site
ALTNAME3	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Third alternative or additional name of the site
SITE_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	[value]	English:2001lewis	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or ND – no data		
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	[value] or ND – no data	OAID-000246	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	English	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR1	int2	[YYYY] – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2001	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol] or Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	Quatern_Int_83-85 or second example Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130 Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e., PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1016/S1040-6182(01)00032-5	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	[value] or	Chen	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
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		<i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		

Sample provenance and characteristics

SEDTYPE	varchar(3) :P:NN	AEN – Aeolian FLV – Fluvial LAC – Lacustrine	FLV	Sedimentary facies, referring to the main mechanism of transportation and deposition and, therefore, determining OCTOPUS/ SahulSed sub-compilation membership.
GEOTYPE	text:P	<i>[geotypeid – value]</i> 1 – Terrace 2 – Floodplain 3 – Alluvial fan 4 – Bench 5 – Island 6 – Slack water deposit	Floodplain 9 – Sandsheet 10 – Beach / Shoreline 11 – Nearshore deposit	Geomorphological type of feature sampled (values 1:7 and 15 are exclusively allowed for “SEDTYPE” == ‘FLV’, values 8:9 are allowed for ‘AEN’ and values 10:14 are allowed for ‘LAC’ sub-compilations, respectively) 14 – Deflated cliff 15 – Bar or

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		7 – Levee 8 – Dune	12 – Lake floor 13 – Lakeshore terrace	-9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
DEPCON	text:P	[<i>depconid</i> – value] 1 – Isolated dune 2 – Dunefield 3 – Aeolian cap on beach ridge 4 – Sandsheet	NULL 5 – Costal shoreline or	Deposition context of feature sampled. Note – “DEPCON” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’. -9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
DUNEFIELD	text	[<i>Name</i>] or ND – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Name of dunefield in which the sample site located. Note – “DUNEFIELD” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’.
GEOMMOD	text:P	[<i>geommodid</i> – value] 0 – No modifier, i.e., ‘normal’ dune 1 – Lacustrine source bordering 2 – Lakefloor 3 – Fluvial source bordering 4 – Obstacle	NULL 5 – Coastal 6 – Blowout	Geomorphic modifier of feature sampled. Note – “GEOMMOD” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’. or -9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
MORPH	text:P	[<i>morphid</i> – value] 0 – no modifier 1 – Climbing 2 – Falling 3 – Foredune 4 – Longitudinal 5 – Lunette 6 – Nebkha	NULL 7 – Network 8 – Parabolic 9 – Sand sheet 10 – Transverse 11 – Transverse shoreline	Morphology of the sampled feature. Note – “MORPH” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’. or -9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
DUNTRND	int2 [°]	[<i>value</i>] or -9999 – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Trend, i.e., orientation of the sampled dune (in degree between 0 and 360). Note – “DUNTRND” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’.
SITETYPE	text:P	[<i>sitetypeid</i> – value] 1 – Outcrop	ND	Type of the site from which samples were extracted.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		2 – Core 3 – Auger/ hole 4 – Pit or Quarry 5 – Artificial excavation (trench)	or	Note – “SITETYPE” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘LAC’. -9999 – ND; for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable
DEPTHICK	float4 [m]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable	1.80	Total length of the core or height of the outcrop. Note – “DEPTHICK” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘LAC’.
SMPDEPTH	numeric(9,2) [m]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable	1.80	Depth below the surface (or datum) from which sample was extracted. If the published sample depth was specified as a range, then the median value for that range is reported here. Note – “SMPDEPTH” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘LAC’.
SED_MAT	varchar(6):P	<i>[grnsizeid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Sand (Sa) 2 – Silt (Si)	Sa 3 – Clay (Cl)	Type of stratigraphic unit sampled or -9999 – for no data
FACIES	text:p	<i>[faciesid – value]</i> 1 – Channel 2 – Overbank 3 – Beach/ Shoreline 4 – Deep-water lacustrine 5 – Shallow-water lacustrine 6 – Near-shore lacustrine 7 – Lacustrine (water depth unclear)	Overbank 8 – Playa 9 – Calcareous deposits	Sedimentological facies type. Note – “FACIES” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘AEN’ (values 1:2 are exclusively allowed for “SEDTYPE” == ‘FLV’; values 3:9 are exclusively allowed for “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’) or -9999 – ND; for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable
LAKETYPE	text:p	<i>[laketypeid – value]</i> 1 – Tectonic lake 2 – Landslide lake 3 – Crater lake 4 – Oxbow lake 5 – Playa lake	<i>NULL</i> 6 – Fen 7 – Swamp 8 – Lagoon	Type of origin of the lake formation. Note – “LAKETYPE” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’. or -9999 – ND; for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
BEACHEI	String [m]	[value] or ND – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Height of the sampled beach ridge (if applicable). For beach ridges <1 m, 1 is recorded here. Note – “BEACHEI” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’.
BEACHAHD	String [m]	[value] or ND – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Australian Height Datum of the sampled beach ridge (if applicable). Note – “BEACHAHD” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’.
SMP_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	ND	Free text sample comment field.
COL_MTD	text:P	[col_mtdid – value] 1 – Auger 2 – Block 3 – Core 4 – Downhole Tube 5 – Excavated	Tube 6 – Tube 7 – Other 8 – InSitu	Sample collection method for OSL dating. ‘InSitu’ = plotted during excavation or removed from section. 9 – Sieve or -9999 – ND; for no data
LUM_MAT	text:P	[lum_matid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Burnt stone (Burnt) 2 – Cobbles (Cobble) 3 – Sediment (Sed) 4 – Rock surface (Surf)	Sediment 5 – Mud wasp nest (Wasp) 6 – for other (Other)	Type of sample material used for OSL and TL dating or -9999 – for no data (ND)
MINERAL	text:P	[mineralid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Calcite/Aragonite (Ca) 2 – Potassium Feldspar (KF) 3 – Sodium Feldspar (NaF)	Quartz 4 – Polymineral (Poly) 5 – Quartz (Q)	Type of mineral used for equivalent dose determination or -9999 – for no data
SIZE_MIN	int2 [µm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	125	Reported minimum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
SIZE_MAX	int2 [μm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	180	Reported maximum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination
H2O_MEAS	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.80	Water content as measured from the sample. “H2O_MEAS” will be -9999.99 for estimated, but not measured water content. For those samples, “H2O_USED” will hold the reported estimated value. If the measured water content is given as <1% in the original publication, then 1.0 was recorded here.
H2O_USED	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.80	Water content used for environmental dose rate determination
H2O_ERR	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	3.00	Standard error for “H2O_USED” (1σ)
Equivalent dose measurements				
OSL_TYPEAB	text:P	[osl_typeid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Infrared Stimulated Lum. (IRSL) 2 – Multiple Elevated Temperature post-Infrared IRSL (MET-pIRIR) 3 – Optically Stimulated Lum. (OSL)	OSL 4 – Post-Infrared IRSL; 2-step (pIRIR) 5 – Thermally Transferred OSL (TT-OSL) 6 – Violet Stimulated Lum. (VSL)	Abbreviated published Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) type used to determine equivalent dose 7 – for undefined OSL type (Other) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
ALIQ_TYPE	varchar(3):P	SG – Single Grain SA – Single Aliquot MA – Multiple Aliquots or ND – for no data	SA	Reported aliquot type used for equivalent dose determination
ALIQ_SIZE	numeric [mm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	-9999.99	Reported size of aliquot diameter in mm

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
ED_PROCABR	text:P	<i>[ed_procid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – ‘Australian Slide’ (AS) 2 – Combined Regenerative and Additive Method (CRAM) 3 – Multiple Aliquot Additive Dose (MAAD)	AVG 4 – Multiple Aliquot Regenerative Dose (MAR) 5 – Single Aliquot Regenerative Dose (SAR)	Abbreviated reported procedure used to determine sample equivalent dose for OSL and TL methods 6 – Single Aliquot Additive Dose (SAAD) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
RESCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Residual dose correction was applied to the Equivalent Dose, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, MET-pIRIR, VSL, and TT-OSL
DOSERECOV	varchar(3):P	Yes No or NA – not applicable ND – for no data	Yes	Were dose recovery test results reported in the study?
AGEMODELAB	text:P	<i>[agemodelid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Average Dose Model (ADM) 2 – Arithmetic Mean (AVG) 3 – Average variance (AVVAR) 4 – Central Age Model (CAM) 5 – Unlogged Central Age Model (CAM_UL) 6 – Common Age Model (COM_AM) 7 – Finite Mixture Model (FMM)	CAM 8 – Internal–External Consistency Criterion (IEU) 9 – Minimum Age Model (MAM) 10 – Unlogged Minimum Age Model (MAM_UL) 11 – Maximum Age Model (MAX)	Abbreviated model used to combine individual equivalent dose estimates for age determination 12 – normalised Median Absolute Deviation Central Age Model (nMAD_CAM) 13 – pdf Gaussian Age Model (PDFG) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
PH1_TEMP	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	240	Preheat temperature applied immediately prior to measurement of either the Natural, Regenerative or Additive dose
PH2_TEMP	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	-9999	Preheat temperature applied immediately prior to measurement of test dose
NUM_MEAS	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i>	-9999	Number of aliquots/grains measured for the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or -9999 – for no data		
NUM_ACC	int2 [°C]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	-9999	Number of aliquots/grains accepted for equivalent dose determination
EQUIVDOSE	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	9.85	Reported equivalent dose in Gy, sometimes referred to as ED, D _e , palaeodose (P) or burial dose
ED_ERR	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.11	Published error for the equivalent dose at 1 standard error (1σ)
ED_INF	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Natural signal projected onto the dose saturation plateau of dose response curve (D _e represented is a minimum value)
OD	numeric	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	5.00	Overdispersion value for equivalent dose dataset calculated as per Galbraith <i>et al.</i> , (1999)
OD_ERR	numeric	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Overdispersion error value (at 1 standard error, 1σ) for equivalent dose data set calculated as per Galbraith <i>et al.</i> , (1999)
OD_TYPE	varchar(3):P	% – Percentage Gy – Gray or ND – for no data	%	The unit of measure for “OD” and “OD_ERR” values
Radionuclide concentrations				
U	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	1.68	Uranium content of the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
U_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the uranium content of the sample
U_MTDAB	text:P	[u_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) 2 – Flame Photometry (F) 3 – In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (FGS) 4 – Combined In-situ Gamma Spectrometry and Neutron Activation Analysis (FGS+NAA) 5 – Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (GMBC) 6 – combined GMBC and FGS results (GMBC+FGS) 7 – High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS) 8 – Combined High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS&FGS) 9 – Combined HRGS and High-resolution alpha-spectrometry (HRGS&HRAS) 10 – Mean of HRGS and XRF (HRGS&XRF) 11 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-A/OES) 12 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) 13 – Combined ICP-MS and –A/OES results (ICP-MS+ICP-A/OES) 14 – Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) 15 – Combined NAA and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry results (NAA+FGS) 16 – Mean of NAA and HRGS (NAA+HRGS) 17 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (NAA+ICP-MS) 18 – Neutron Activation Analysis (+Potassium) (NAA+K) 19 – Mean of NAA and TSAC (NAA+TSAC) 20 – Mean of NAA and XRF (NAA+XRF) 21 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (TSAC) 22 – Thick Source Alpha Counting + Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (TSAC+GMBC) 23 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (+Potassium) (TSAC+K) 24 – X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) 25 – Other (Other) 26 – TBA (DNA+TSAC) 27 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (NAA+ICP-A/OES) 28 – Combined X-ray Fluorescence and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (XRF+ICP-A/OES) 29 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (+Potassium) (NAA+ICP-MS+K) 31 – Flame Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (F-AES) 32 – Combined AES and XRF results (AES+XRF) or -9999 – no data (ND) -9991 – not applicable (NA)	ICP-MS	Abbreviated method used to determine uranium content of the sample in data field “U”. Note 1 – NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA. Note 2 – lookup table behind “U_MTDAB” serves other fields/methods too, i.e., is not exclusively serving “U”
TH	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	4.40	Thorium content of the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
TH_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the thorium content of the sample
TH_MTDAB	text:P	[th_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ICP-MS	Method used to determine thorium content of the sample in data field “TH”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
K	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.40	Potassium content of the sample. N.B. K not K ₂ O
K_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the potassium content of the sample
K_MTDAB	text:P	[k_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ICP-A/OES	Method used to determine potassium content of the sample in data field “K”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
High Resolution Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS) activities				
U238	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³⁸ U content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
U238_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “U238”
RA226	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁶ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA226_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA226”

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
PB210	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²¹⁰ Pb content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
PB210_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “PB210”
RA228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA228”
TH228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH228”
TH232	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³² Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH232_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH232”
K40	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	⁴⁰ K content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
K40_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	-9999.99	Published error value for “K40”

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or -9999.99 – for no data		
External dose rate measurements				
ALPH	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External alpha dose rate (wet)
ALPH_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external alpha dose rate
ALPH_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[alph_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	NA	Abbreviated method used to determine external alpha dose rate. If study authors have specified that the grains were HF etched, then “ALPH_MTD” will be ‘NA’ (due to the alpha-irradiated surface of the grains being removed). <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
BETA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External beta dose rate (wet)
BETA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external beta dose rate
BETA_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[beta_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine external beta dose rate <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
GAMMA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External gamma dose rate (wet)
GAMMA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external gamma dose rate

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
GAMMA_MTDA	text:P	<i>[gamma_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Method used to determine external gamma dose rate Note that the NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA.
COSMIC	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.14	Cosmic dose rate (wet)
COSMIC_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.01	1 standard error (1σ) for cosmic dose rate
Internal dose rate measurements				
ALPH_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal alpha dose rate (from within grain)
ALPH_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for internal alpha dose rate
ALPH_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal alpha dose rate assumed or measured?
BETA_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal beta dose rate (from within grain)
BETA_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for internal beta dose rate
BETA_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured	ND	Was the internal beta dose rate assumed or measured?

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or ND – for no data		
DIFF_DOSE	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Whether a different and/or additional method, not specified in this compilation was used to determine the dosimetry for this sample
Total dose rate				
DOSERATE	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	1.278	Total (wet) environmental dose rate used for age determination
DOSE_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.049	Total (wet) environmental dose rate error at 1σ
Age determination				
OSL_AGE	numeric [ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	7.70	Published OSL age
OSL_RNDERR	numeric [ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published Random only “OSL_AGE” error
OSL_ERR	numeric [ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.30	Published total “OSL_AGE” error (random + systematic)
AGE_CI	varchar(3):P	1s – 1 standard error [1σ] 2s – 2 standard error [2σ] SD – Standard Deviation or ND – for no data	1s	Published confidence interval on the age estimate

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
FADCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	ND	“OSL_AGE” was corrected for fading, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, and MET-pIRIR
G_VAL	numeric [%/10a]	[value; one decimal place] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Represents the correcting approach using value of fading rate in feldspars. If reported, express as percent per decade.
G_VAL_ERR	numeric [%/10a]	[value; one decimal place] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published 1σ error for the “G_VAL”
AGE_COMMT	text	[value] or NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Free text age comment field.

Table S3

Database field descriptions: SahulSed TL

OCTOPUSdata/ Sahul Sedimentary Archives/ TL collection (aeolian, fluvial, lacustrine). Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	SED_AEN_TL#### SED_FLV_TL#### SED_LAC_TL####	SED_FLV_TL0494	Unique age identifier provided as part of the sub-compilation. "OBSID1" membership → AEN (aeolian), FLV (fluvial), LAC (lacustrine); Method → OSL (Optically Stimulated Luminescence), TL (Thermoluminescence)
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	ColyTL_32	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample. Samples labelled only by numbers in the literature (e.g., 1, 2, 3 etc) have had a compound prefix – first three author name letters AND double-digit publication year – added (e.g., 'Nan87_1' for sample 1 (Nanson 1987)).
LABID	text	[value] or ND – no data	W3627	Unique lab code assigned by the lab where age was determined. For radiocarbon (and for many luminescence) labs, the first part of the lab code refers to the determining facility.
LAB_FACLT	text:P	[value]	UOW TL Dating Lab. Wollongong	Name of the laboratory where age was determined (where deducible from "LABID")
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	10.25900/2a76-vw55	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[SEDSM#####<suffix>]	SEDSM02603	Sample identifier provided as part of the compilation. SahulSed SMPIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated "X_WGS84" AND "Y_WGS84" AND "SITENAME" AND "SMPDEPTH". Re suffixes – '_pre' indicates that the matching age is preferred by the authors of the original publication; '_alt' tags alternatives to '_pre' ages; and '.t'

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
				indicates the existence of a corresponding OSL ('o') measurement on the same sample.
SITEID	text:NN	[SEDST####o.x]	SEDST0487t.a	Unique sample identifier that serves database operation. SahulSed SITEIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated "SITENAME" AND "ALTNAME1". Suffixes 'o' resp. 't' indicate OSL or TL membership, respectively, with running alphabetic letters added for ID uniqueness.
METASITEID	text	[value]	NA	Unique metasite identifier provided as part of the compilation. Not applicable for SahulSed compilations
METANAME	text	[value]	NA	Metasite name
METHODABBR	text:P:NN	[methodid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Amino Acid Racemization (AAR) 2 – Radiocarbon Dating (C14) 3 – Cation Ratio Dating (CRD) 4 – Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)	TL 5 – Oxidisable Carbon Ratio (OCR) 6 – Optically Stimulated Lum. (OSL) 7 – Thermoluminescence (TL) 8 – Uranium-Series (U)	9 – Closed-system U-Series and ESR model (CSU-ESR) 10 – Stratigraphic correlation (Strat) 11 – Coupled U-ESR model (U-ESR)
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value] or ND – no data	ND	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	AUS TSI – Torres Strait Islands	Refers to Sahul region. Same as "CNTRY" but needed to accommodate for 'TSI' or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia	AU-NT PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
LAKE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of lake where study site is located
BASIN	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Billabong-Yanco Creeks	Name of river basin where study site is located

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	MDB	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	MDB_11	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGFL1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Billabong-Yanco Creeks	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Murray-Darling Basin	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	RIV	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Riverina	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	145.823831	WGS84 longitude of the site
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-34.770635	WGS84 latitude of the site
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description	INTP_INTP	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data		'ORIG_', or 'ND_'. Second part of value refers to "ELEVATION" ('_INTP', or '_ORIG', or '_ND'). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value] or -9999 – no data	116	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITENAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Murrumbidgee River	Name of the site
SITE_SPEC	text	[value] or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text field that allows for a brief description of the site
ALTNAME1	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	Boona	First alternative or additional name of the site (e.g., published under previous name etc.)
ALTNAME2	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	Property 78	Second alternative or additional name of the site
ALTNAME3	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	KPHA_10	Third alternative or additional name of the site
SITE_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	[value]	Pucillo:2005coleambally	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or ND – no data		
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	[value] or ND – no data	OAID-000366	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Pucillo	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR1	int2	[YYYY] – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2005	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol] or Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	phdthesis or second example Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e., PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html
			Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	[value] or	NULL	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
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		<i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		

Sample provenance and characteristics

SEDTYPE	varchar(3) :P:NN	AEN – Aeolian FLV – Fluvial LAC – Lacustrine	FLV	Sedimentary facies, referring to the main mechanism of transportation and deposition and, therefore, determining OCTOPUS/ SahulSed sub-compilation membership.
GEOTYPE	text:P	<i>[geotypeid – value]</i> 1 – Terrace 2 – Floodplain 3 – Alluvial fan 4 – Bench 5 – Island 6 – Slack water deposit	ND 9 – Sandsheet 10 – Beach / Shoreline 11 – Nearshore deposit	Geomorphological type of feature sampled (values 1:7 and 15 are exclusively allowed for “SEDTYPE” == ‘FLV’, values 8:9 are allowed for ‘AEN’ and values 10:14 are allowed for ‘LAC’ sub-compilations, respectively) 14 – Deflated cliff 15 – Bar or

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		7 – Levee 8 – Dune	12 – Lake floor 13 – Lakeshore terrace	-9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
DEPCON	text:P	[<i>depconid</i> – value] 1 – Isolated dune 2 – Dunefield 3 – Aeolian cap on beach ridge 4 – Sandsheet	NULL 5 – Costal shoreline or	Deposition context of feature sampled. Note – “DEPCON” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’. -9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
DUNEFIELD	text	[<i>Name</i>] or ND – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Name of dunefield in which the sample site located. Note – “DUNEFIELD” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’.
GEOMMOD	text:P	[<i>geommodid</i> – value] 0 – No modifier, i.e., ‘normal’ dune 1 – Lacustrine source bordering 2 – Lakefloor 3 – Fluvial source bordering 4 – Obstacle	NULL 5 – Coastal 6 – Blowout	Geomorphic modifier of feature sampled. Note – “GEOMMOD” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’. or -9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
MORPH	text:P	[<i>morphid</i> – value] 0 – no modifier 1 – Climbing 2 – Falling 3 – Foredune 4 – Longitudinal 5 – Lunette 6 – Nebkha	NULL 7 – Network 8 – Parabolic 9 – Sand sheet 10 – Transverse 11 – Transverse shoreline	Morphology of the sampled feature. Note – “MORPH” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’. or -9999 – ND; for no data NULL – for not applicable
DUNTRND	int2 [°]	[<i>value</i>] or -9999 – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Trend, i.e., orientation of the sampled dune (in degree between 0 and 360). Note – “DUNTRND” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’.
SITETYPE	text:P	[<i>sitetypeid</i> – value] 1 – Outcrop	ND	Type of the site from which samples were extracted.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		<p>2 – Core 3 – Auger/ hole</p> <p>4 – Pit or Quarry 5 – Artificial excavation (trench)</p>	or	<p>Note – “SITETYPE” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘LAC’.</p> <p>-9999 – ND; for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable</p>
DEPTHICK	float4 [m]	<p>[value; two decimal places]</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999.99 – for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable</p>	-9999.99	Total length of the core or height of the outcrop. Note – “DEPTHICK” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘LAC’.
SMPDEPTH	numeric(9,2) [m]	<p>[value; two decimal places]</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999.99 – for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable</p>	2.90	Depth below the surface (or datum) from which sample was extracted. If the published sample depth was specified as a range, then the median value for that range is reported here. Note – “SMPDEPTH” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘LAC’.
SED_MAT	varchar(6):P	<p>[grnsizeid – value (abbreviation)]</p> <p>1 – Sand (Sa) 2 – Silt (Si)</p>	<p>Sa</p> <p>3 – Clay (Cl)</p>	<p>Type of stratigraphic unit sampled</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999 – for no data</p>
FACIES	text:p	<p>[faciesid – value]</p> <p>1 – Channel 2 – Overbank 3 – Beach / Shoreline 4 – Deep-water lacustrine 5 – Shallow-water lacustrine</p> <p>6 – Near-shore lacustrine 7 – Lacustrine (water depth unclear)</p>	<p>Channel</p> <p>8 – Playa 9 – Calcareous deposits</p>	<p>Sedimentological facies type.</p> <p>Note – “FACIES” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘FLV’ or ‘LAC’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘AEN’ (values 1:2 are exclusively allowed for “SEDTYPE” == ‘FLV’; values 3:9 are exclusively allowed for “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’)</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999 – ND; for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable</p>
LAKETYPE	text:p	<p>[laketypeid – value]</p> <p>1 – Tectonic lake 2 – Landslide lake</p> <p>3 – Crater lake 4 – Oxbow lake 5 – Playa lake</p>	<p><i>NULL</i></p> <p>6 – Fen 7 – Swamp 8 – Lagoon</p>	<p>Type of origin of the lake formation.</p> <p>Note – “LAKETYPE” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’, i.e., must be <i>NULL</i> for ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’.</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999 – ND; for no data <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable</p>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
BEACHEI	String [m]	[value] or ND – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Height of the sampled beach ridge (if applicable). For beach ridges <1 m, 1 is recorded here. Note – “BEACHEI” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’.
BEACHAHD	String [m]	[value] or ND – for no data NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Australian Height Datum of the sampled beach ridge (if applicable). Note – “BEACHAHD” field only usable if “SEDTYPE” == ‘LAC’, i.e., must be NULL for ‘AEN’ or ‘FLV’.
SMP_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	ND	Free text sample comment field.
COL_MTD	text:P	[col_mtdid – value] 1 – Auger 2 – Block 3 – Core 4 – Downhole Tube 5 – Excavated	Tube 6 – Tube 7 – Other 8 – InSitu	Sample collection method for TL dating. ‘InSitu’ = plotted during excavation or removed from section. 9 – Sieve or -9999 – ND; for no data
LUM_MAT	text:P	[lum_matid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Burnt stone (Burnt) 2 – Cobbles (Cobble) 3 – Sediment (Sed) 4 – Rock surface (Surf)	Sediment 5 – Mud wasp nest (Wasp) 6 – for other (Other)	Type of sample material used for OSL and TL dating or -9999 – for no data (ND)
MINERAL	text:P	[mineralid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Calcite/Aragonite (Ca) 2 – Potassium Feldspar (KF) 3 – Sodium Feldspar (NaF)	Quartz 4 – Polymineral (Poly) 5 – Quartz (Q)	Type of mineral used for equivalent dose determination or -9999 – for no data
SIZE_MIN	int2 [µm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	90	Reported minimum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
SIZE_MAX	int2 [μm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	125	Reported maximum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination
H2O_MEAS	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	11.50	Water content as measured from the sample. “H2O_MEAS” will be -9999.99 for estimated, but not measured water content. For those samples, “H2O_USED” will hold the reported estimated value. If the measured water content is given as <1% in the original publication, then 1.0 was recorded here.
H2O_USED	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	11.50	Water content used for environmental dose rate determination
H2O_ERR	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	3.00	Standard error for “H2O_USED” (1σ)
Equivalent dose measurements				
ALIQ_SIZE	numeric [mm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	-9999.99	Reported size of aliquot diameter in mm
ED_PROCABR	text:P	[ed_procid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – ‘Australian Slide’ (AS) 2 – Combined Regenerative and Additive Method (CRAM) 3 – Multiple Aliquot Additive Dose (MAAD)	CRAM 4 – Multiple Aliquot Regenerative Dose (MAR) 5 – Single Aliquot Regenerative Dose (SAR)	Abbreviated reported procedure used to determine sample equivalent dose for OSL and TL methods 6 – Single Aliquot Additive Dose (SAAD) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
RESCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Residual dose correction was applied to the Equivalent Dose, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, MET-pIRIR, VSL, and TT-OSL

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
AGEMODELAB	text:P	<i>[agemodelid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Average Dose Model (ADM) 2 – Arithmetic Mean (AVG) 3 – Average variance (AVVAR) 4 – Central Age Model (CAM) 5 – Unlogged Central Age Model (CAM_UL) 6 – Common Age Model (COM_AM) 7 – Finite Mixture Model (FMM)	AVG 8 – Internal–External Consistency Criterion (IEU) 9 – Minimum Age Model (MAM) 10 – Unlogged Minimum Age Model (MAM_UL) 11 – Maximum Age Model (MAX)	Abbreviated model used to combine individual equivalent dose estimates for age determination 12 – normalised Median Absolute Deviation Central Age Model (nMAD_CAM) 13 – pdf Gaussian Age Model (PDFG) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
PLAT_REG	varchar(9) [°C]	<i>[range]</i> or ND – for no data	300-500	Pre-heat plateau region
AN_TEMP	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	375	Specific temperature at which analysis is performed
NUM_MEAS	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	-9999	Number of aliquots/grains measured for the sample
EQUIVDOSE	numeric [Gy]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	227	Reported equivalent dose in Gy, sometimes referred to as ED, D _e , palaeodose (P) or burial dose
ED_ERR	numeric [Gy]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	9	Published error for the equivalent dose at 1 standard error (1σ)
ED_SAT	numeric [Gy]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Equivalent dose (ED) for the saturated age
ED_SATERR	numeric [Gy]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published 1σ error for the saturated age

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Radionuclide concentrations				
U	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Uranium content of the sample
U_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the uranium content of the sample
U_MTDAB	text:P	[u_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) 2 – Flame Photometry (F) 3 – In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (FGS) 4 – Combined In-situ Gamma Spectrometry and Neutron Activation Analysis (FGS+NAA) 5 – Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (GMBC) 6 – combined GMBC and FGS results (GMBC+FGS) 7 – High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS) 8 – Combined High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS&FGS) 9 – Combined HRGS and High-resolution alpha-spectrometry (HRGS&HRAS) 10 – Mean of HRGS and XRF (HRGS&XRF) 11 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-A/OES) 12 – Thick Source Alpha Counting + Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (TSAC+GMBC) 13 – Combined ICP-MS and –A/OES results (ICP-MS+ICP-A/OES) 14 – Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) 15 – Combined NAA and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry results (NAA+FGS) 16 – Mean of NAA and HRGS (NAA+HRGS) 17 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (NAA+ICP-MS) 18 – Neutron Activation Analysis (+Potassium) (NAA+K) 19 – Mean of NAA and TSAC (NAA+TSAC) 20 – Mean of NAA and XRF (NAA+XRF) 21 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (TSAC) 22 – Thick Source Alpha Counting + Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (TSAC+GMBC) 23 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (+Potassium) (TSAC+K) 24 – X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) 25 – Other (Other) 26 – TBA (DNA+TSAC) 27 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (NAA+ICP-A/OES) 28 – Combined X-ray Fluorescence and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (XRF+ICP-A/OES) 29 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (+Potassium) (NAA+ICP-MS+K) 31 – Flame Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (F-AES) 32 – Combined AES and XRF results (AES+XRF) or -9999 – no data (ND) -9991 – not applicable (NA)	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine uranium content of the sample in data field “U”. Note 1 – NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA. Note 2 – lookup table behind “U_MTDAB” serves other fields/methods too, i.e., is not exclusively serving “U”

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		12 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)		
TH	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Thorium content of the sample
TH_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the thorium content of the sample
TH_MTDAB	text:P	[th_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Method used to determine thorium content of the sample in data field “TH”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
U_TH	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	92.00	When U and Th elemental content are reported together, rather than separate U and Th. Reported as radioactive element specific activity
U_TH_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	2.90	Published error for “U_TH” specific activity
U_TH_MTD	text:P	[u_th_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	TSAC	Method used to determine “U_TH” specific activity of the sample in the field “U_TH” <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
K	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	2.46	Potassium content of the sample. N.B. K not K ₂ O
K_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.05	Standard error (1σ) for the potassium content of the sample
K_MTDAB	text:P	k_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ICP-A/OES	Method used to determine potassium content of the sample in data field “K”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
RB	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value] or -9999.99 – for no data	100	Rubidium (Rb) content
High Resolution Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS) activities				
U238	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³⁸ U content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
U238_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “U238”
RA226	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁶ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA226_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA226”
PB210	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²¹⁰ Pb content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
PB210_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “PB210”
RA228	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA228”

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
TH228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH228”
TH232	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³² Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH232_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH232”
K40	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	⁴⁰ K content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
K40_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “K40”
External dose rate measurements				
ALPH	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External alpha dose rate (wet)
ALPH_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external alpha dose rate
ALPH_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[alph_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine external alpha dose rate. If study authors have specified that the grains were HF etched, then “ALPH_MTD” will be ‘NA’ (due to the alpha-irradiated surface of the grains being removed).

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
				<i>Refer to "U_MTDAB" for values and description!</i>
BETA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External beta dose rate (wet)
BETA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external beta dose rate
BETA_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[beta_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to "U_MTDAB" for values!	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine external beta dose rate <i>Refer to "U_MTDAB" for values and description!</i>
GAMMA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External gamma dose rate (wet)
GAMMA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external gamma dose rate
GAMMA_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[gamma_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to "U_MTDAB" for values!	ND	Method used to determine external gamma dose rate Note that the NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA.
COSMIC	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.15	Cosmic dose rate (wet)
COSMIC_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for cosmic dose rate
Internal dose rate measurements				
ALPH_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or	-9999.99	Internal alpha dose rate (from within grain)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		-9999.99 – for no data		
ALPH_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for internal alpha dose rate
ALPH_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal alpha dose rate assumed or measured?
BETA_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal beta dose rate (from within grain)
BETA_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for internal beta dose rate
BETA_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal beta dose rate assumed or measured?
DIFF_DOSE	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Whether a different and/or additional method, not specified in this compilation was used to determine the dosimetry for this sample
Total dose rate				
DOSERATE	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	4.143	Total (wet) environmental dose rate used for age determination
DOSE_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.064	Total (wet) environmental dose rate error at 1σ

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Age determination				
TL_AGE	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	54.8	Published TL age
TL_RNDERR	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published Random only “TL_AGE” error
TL_ERR	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	2.3	Published total “TL_AGE” error (random + systematic)
AGE_CI	varchar(3):P	1s – 1 standard error [1 σ] 2s – 2 standard error [2 σ] SD – Standard Deviation or ND – for no data	1s	Published confidence interval on the age estimate
FADCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	ND	“TL_AGE” was corrected for fading, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, and MET-pIRIR
G_VAL	numeric [%/10a]	[value; one decimal place] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Represents the correcting approach using value of fading rate in feldspars. If reported, express as percent per decade.
G_VAL_ERR	numeric [%/10a]	[value; one decimal place] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published 1 σ error for the “G_VAL”
AGE_COMMT	text	[value] or NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Free text age comment field.

Table S4

Database field descriptions: SahulArch Radiocarbon

OCTOPUSdata/ Sahul Archaeology/ Radiocarbon collection. Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	[ARCH#####AAR###] – for AAR [ARCH#####C14###] – for C14 [ARCH#####CRD###] – for CRD [ARCH#####ESR###] – for ESR [ARCH#####OCR###] – for OCR [ARCH#####OSL###] – for OSL [ARCH#####TL###] – for TL [ARCH#####U###] – for U-series	ARCH0001C14001	Unique age identifier provided as part of the compilation. The first part of the identifier (i.e., ARCH####) is linked to “SITEID”, the ID of the site. The second part of the identifier is unique to the database entry and does also include abbreviation given to the method used to produce the age. For method abbreviations see “METHOD”.
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	ND	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample. Samples labelled only by numbers in the literature (e.g. 1, 2, 3 etc) have had a compound prefix – first three author name letters AND double-digit publication year – added (e.g. ‘Nan87_1’ for sample 1 (Nanson 1987)).
LABID	text	[value] or ND – no data	OZQ-464	Unique lab code assigned by the lab where age was determined. For radiocarbon (and for many luminescence) labs, the first part of the lab code refers to the determining facility.
LAB_FACLT	text:P	[value]	ANSTO-ANTARES	Name of the laboratory where age was determined (where deducible from “LABID”)
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	10.25900/2mb4-rr36	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[ARCH#####SMP###x]	ARCH0001SMP063a	Sample identifier provided as part of the compilation. The first part of the identifier (i.e., ARCH####) is linked to “SITEID”, the ID of the site.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
				Where it is clear that two or more observations (dates/ rates) have been measured on one sample, they have the same "SMPID" but a different "OBSID1". This also applies across methods, e.g., one sample with an OSL age and an U-series age will have the same "SMPID" but different "OBSID1" (i.e. ARCH####OSL### and ARCH####U###).
SITEID	text:NN	[ARCH####x]	ARCH0001a	Unique site identifier provided as part of the compilation
METASITEID	text	[META_ARCH####]	META_ARCH0001	Unique metasite identifier provided as part of the compilation
METANAME	text	[value]	Madjedbebe	Metasite name
METHODABBR	text:P:NN	[methodid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Amino Acid Racemization (AAR) 2 – Radiocarbon Dating (C14) 3 – Cation Ratio Dating (CRD) 4 – Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) 5 – Oxidisable Carbon Ratio (OCR)	C14	Abbreviated type of method used in age determination 6 – Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) 7 – Thermoluminescence (TL) 8 – Uranium-Series (U) 9 – Closed-system U-Series and ESR model (CSU-ESR) 10 – Stratigraphic correlation (Strat) 11 – Coupled U-ESR model (U-ESR)
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	AUS TSI – Torres Strait Islands	Refers to Sahul region. Same as "CNTRY" but needed to accommodate for 'TSI' or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania	AU-NT PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
LAKE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of lake where study site is located
BASIN	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	East Alligator River	Name of river basin where study site is located

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		NA – for not applicable		
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS_20	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGLF1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	East Alligator River	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Tanami-Timor Sea Coast	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	PCK	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Pine Creek	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	150.901171	WGS84 longitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i> <i>Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.</i>
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-34.414173	WGS84 latitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i> <i>Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.</i>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data	ORIG_INTP	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or ‘ORIG_’, or ‘ND_’). Second part of value refers to “ELEVATION” (‘_INTP’, or ‘_ORIG’, or ‘_ND’). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999 – no data	38.7	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITENAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Madjedbebe	Name of the site
SITE_SPEC	text	[value] or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Further specifies information given in “SITENAME”
ALTNAME1	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	Malakunanja II	First alternative or additional name of the site (e.g., published under previous name etc.)
ALTNAME2	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	Djawumba 3	Second alternative or additional name of the site
ALTNAME3	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Third alternative or additional name of the site
SITECODE	text:P	[sitecodeid – value] 1 – Stone artefact deposit 2 – Burial (animal) 3 – Burial (human)	Rockshelter or cave 8 – Open site	Site type characterising the dominant attribute of the site. For example, burials in a rockshelter with lots of occupation deposit would be classified as a Rockshelter, not a Cemetery. 13 – Stone structure

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		4 – Cemetery 5 – Earth mound 6 – Hearth (isolated) 7 – Shell midden	9 – Quarry 10 – Rock art 11 – Rockshelter or cave 12 – Culturally modified tree	19 – Other or -9999 – no data (ND)
OPENCLOSED	varchar(6):P	Open Closed or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Closed	This field records whether the site was closed (i.e., a rockshelter, cave or other enclosed site) or open (i.e., an artefact scatter, midden on a beach etc.), and is used in the application of taphonomic techniques in time-series analysis. Please note that 'Closed' does not relate to availability or accessibility of information.
SITE_COMMT	text	<i>[value]</i> or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	Clarkson:2017occupation	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	OAID-000224	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Clarkson	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR1	int2	<i>[YYYY]</i> – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2017	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	<i>[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol]</i> or	Nature_547 or second example	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e., PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130 Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1038/nature22968	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	[value] or <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable	Roberts	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
Sample provenance and characteristics				
FEATDATED	text:P	<i>[featdatedid – value]</i> 1 – Hearth 2 – Burial (animal) 3 – Burial (human)	not related to a feature 4 – Mud wasp nest 5 – Rock art 9 – Other	Specific feature dated, where applicable. or 999 – for not related to a feature -9999 – no data (ND)
SQUARE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	C3	Square or trench designation from where the sample is from.
XU	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	4	Excavation Unit (“XU”) or spit designation from where the sample is from.
SMPDEPTH	numeric(9,2) [m]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	0.08	Depth below the surface (or datum) from which sample was extracted. If the published sample depth was specified as a range, then the median value for that range is reported here.
SMPX_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	<i>[value; six decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	149.074222	WGS84 longitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>
SMPY_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	<i>[value; six decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-35.678042	WGS84 latitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>
OCCUPATION	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	No	Is the dated sample directly related to human activity (e.g. hearth, organic artefact, burial), or was it simply part of a wider archaeological deposit

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		NA – for not applicable		
CONTEXT	varchar(10):P	Occupation Sterile or ND – no data	Occupation	Was the sample collected from a stratigraphic unit that is associated with human 'Occupation' or one that was culturally 'Sterile'.
SMP_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text sample comment field.
COL_MTD	text:P	[col_mtdid – value] 1 – Auger 2 – Block 3 – Core 4 – Downhole Tube 5 – Excavated	InSitu 6 – Tube 7 – Other 8 – InSitu	Sample collection method for ¹⁴ C dating. 'InSitu' = plotted during excavation or removed from section. 9 – Sieve or -9999 – ND; for no data
MATERIAL1	text:P	[materia1id – value(abbreviation)] 1 – Biogenic Carbonate (CarbBio) 2 – Inorganic Carbonate (CarbInorg) 3 – Charred Plant (Charred) 4 – Faunal (Faunal) 5 – Oxalate (Oxalate)	Charred 6 – Paint (Paint) 7 – Plant (Plant) 8 – Sediment (Sediment) 9 – for other (Other)	Type of sample material used for ¹⁴ C dating 10 – Bulk (Mix of materials) or -9999 – no data (ND)
MATERIAL2	text:P	[materia2id – value] 1 – Bark 2 – Beeswax 3 – Binder 4 – Bone 5 – Calcined bone 6 – Calcium soil carbonate 7 – Celtis seed 8 – Coral 9 – Dentine 10 – Egg shell 11 – Enamel	ND 14 – Hair 15 – Marine shell 16 – Nut 17 – Otolith 18 – Peat 19 – Pigment 20 – Pollen 21 – Resin	Type of sample material used for ¹⁴ C dating. Note that if a seed is isolated and dated from a peat sediment, the material dated is 'Seed' not 'Peat'. 24 – Terrestrial snail 25 – Tooth dentine 26 – Tooth enamel 27 – Tufa 28 – Wood 29 – Bulk (Mix of materials) 99 – for other

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		12 – Foraminifera 13 – Freshwater shell	22 – Seed 23 – Speleothem	or -9999 – no data (ND)
BURNT	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	Yes	Whether the material dated was burnt. Note that charcoal = 'Yes'. Calcinated bone – typically white, whilst burnt bone is black – is different to burnt bone, and so is listed in "MATERIAL2" field.
ARCHSPECIS	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	ND	Genus and/ or species, i.e., scientific name of animal or plant used for ¹⁴ C dating
ORGPART	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	ND	Bone element, wood part etc. – e.g., 'Sapwood', 'Heartwood', 'Twig', 'Ring number', 'Femur' ...
HUM_MOD	text:P	<i>[hum_modid – value]</i> 1 – Yes 10 – Artefact 100 – Bead 101 – String 102 – Boomerang 103 – Point 104 – Hook	No 109 – Other artefact 11 – Cut marked 19 – Other	Does indication of human modification exist? Note that charcoal is not considered humanly modified in this field. Association with human activity for e.g., charcoal from hearth features is captured in the site information part ("OCCUPATION") of the database. 2 – No or -9999 – no data
SINGULAR	varchar(3):P	Yes No NA – single entities do not exist, i.e., for example sediment or ND – no data	ND	Was a single entity (e.g., a single piece of charcoal, not several pieces found close to each other) dated, or were several pieces bulked together?
CONSERV	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	No	Was the sample conserved? For example, was it glued or soaked in a consolidant?

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
AGEMTD	varchar(4):P	AMS – Accelerator Mass Spectrometry CONV - Conventional or ND – no data	AMS	Measurement method. Conventional includes liquid scintillation and gas proportional
Physical pretreatment				
PHYSCLEAN	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	Yes	Was the sample physically cleaned? For example, was the surface removed from bone (= 'Yes'), were rootlets and sediment removed from charcoal (= 'Yes').
Chemical pretreatment				
CONTAM	text:P	[<i>contamid</i> – value] 1 – Glue 2 – Conservative 3 – Rootlets 4 – Sediment	ND 5 – Recrystallised material 9 – for other	Did the study authors suggest a specific contaminant may remain after pretreatment? or -9999 – no data (ND)
CHEMPREPAB	text:P	[<i>chemprepid</i> – abbreviation] 1 – ABA 2 – ABA (base soluble) 3 – ABA and bleach 4 – ABA and bleach-SC 5 – ABA-SC 6 – ABOx 7 – ABOx-SC 8 – Acid 9 – Acid (to extract apatite) 10 – Acid or ABA gelatinisation- ultrafiltration 11 – Acid or ABA-gelatinisation 12 – Alpha cellulose 13 – Alpha cellulose-SC 14 – AOX 15 – AOX-SC 16 – CARDS	ABA	Abbreviated type of chemical pretreatment given to the sample. Methods capture the majority of methods applied in Australia. There may be considerable variation within each pretreatment code. 'ABA' (acid-base-acid) is equivalent to 'AAA' (acid-alkali-acid). 'ABOx-SC' = acid-base-oxidation-stepped-combustion. 'HyPy' = hydrogen pyrolysis. 'Acid-gelatinisation' = the Longin method. 'CARDS' = Carbonate Density Separation. 'XAD' = resin used to clean amino acids. Note that 'XAD' flag overwrites potential other pretreatment. Plasma oxidation and potassium permanganate methods refer to methods which aim to convert a specific portion of the sample to CO ₂ and may involve a variety of other steps. 'Bulk' = Several fragments dated together, 'SC' = Stepped combustion, 'Ultra' = Ultrafiltration, 'Longin' = Modified Longing method, 'Gelatin' = Gelatinisation, 'Coll' = Collagen

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		17 – CARDS + acid 18 – Hydroxyproline 19 – HyPy 20 – Plasma Oxidation 21 – Potassium permanganate (to extract oxalate) 22 – Stepped hydrolysis 23 – XAD 24 – AAA	25 – AAA/ABA 26 – AAA/ABA/Acid 27 – ABAu 28 – Bulk 29 – Coll_SC 30 – Coll_ultra 31 – Gelatin 32 – Longin	33 – No 34 – Ultra 99 – Other or -9991 – no applicable (NA) -9999 – no data (ND)
SOLVENT1	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	No	Was the pretreatment preceded by a solvent extraction
SOLVENT2	text:P	<i>[solvent2id – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Methanol (Met) 2 – Ethanol (Eth) 3 – Chloroform (Chl) 4 – Dichloromethane (Dic) 5 – Toluene (Tol) 6 – Hexane (Hex) 7 – Chloroform:Methanol (Chl:Met)	ND or Chl:Met or Met,Tol,Hex 8 – Dichloromethane:Methanol (Dic:Met) 9 – for other (Other)	Abbreviated solvents used. ‘Chl:Met’ and ‘Dic:Met’ refer to mixtures of the named solvents. ‘Met,Tol,Hex’ would indicate sequential use of the named solvents. Note that the conditions used when undertaking a solvent wash vary greatly between laboratories and the impact of the method will vary. or -9999 – no data (ND)
Quality assurance data				
YIELD_MG	numeric [mg]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Amount of material after pretreatment in mg. If a range was used for a particular sample or (more commonly) all samples, the average for the range given is reported here.
YIELD_PCT	numeric [%]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Amount of material after pretreatment in %
C	numeric [mg]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	mg of carbon dated

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
C_ERR	numeric [mg]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured mg carbon dated
C_MTD	text:P	[c_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine mg carbon dated or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
PCT_C	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Measured %C of the pretreated sample
PCT_C_ERR	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured %C of the pretreated sample
PCT_C_MTD	text:P	[pct_c_mtid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine %C of the pretreated sample or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
PCT_N	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Measured %N of the pretreated sample
PCT_N_ERR	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured %N of the pretreated sample
PCT_N_MTD	text:P	[c_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine %N of the pretreated sample or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
CN_RATIO	numeric	[value, two decimal places] or	-9999.99	Measured atomic C:N ratio of the pretreated sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		-9999.99 – no data		
CN_ERR	numeric	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured CN value of the pretreated sample
CN_MTD	text:P	<i>[cn_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine CN ratio of the pretreated sample or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
C13	numeric [‰]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-25.1	Measured $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the pretreated sample. Note that $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value on graphite is not included as it is not equivalent to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ on the pretreated material.
C13_ERR	numeric [‰]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the pretreated sample. Note that $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value on graphite is not included as it is not equivalent to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ on the pretreated material.
C13_MTD	text:P	<i>[c13_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	IR mass spectrometry 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the pretreated sample. Note that $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value on graphite is not included as it is not always equivalent to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ on the pretreated material. or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
O18	numeric [‰]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the of the pretreated sample
O18_ERR	numeric [‰]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the pretreated sample
O18_MTD	text:P	<i>[o18_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the pretreated sample or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
N15	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of the of the pretreated sample
N15_ERR	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of the pretreated sample
N15_MTD	text:P	[n15_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of the pretreated sample or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
S34	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Measured $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ of the of the pretreated sample
S34_ERR	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ of the of the pretreated sample.
S34_MTD	text:P	[s34_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – IR mass spectrometry (IRMS) 2 – Elemental analyser (Elemt) 3 – CRD spectroscopy (CRDS)	ND 4 – Volumetric (Vol) 5 – for other (Other)	Method used to determine $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ of the pretreated sample or -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
RECRYST	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	No	Is secondary recrystallisation present in the pretreated carbonate sample?
PCT_RE_VAL	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or 998 – Calcite/ recrystallization identified using stain or microscopy -991 – NO calcite/ recrystallization identified using stain or microscopy	-9999.99	Calcite/recrystallised mineral in the pretreated carbonate sample. Stain or microscopy methods used: 998 = presence of calcite/ recrystallization verified, or -991 = absence of calcite/ recrystallization.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or -9999.99 – no data		
PCT_RE_ERR	numeric [%]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for measured amount of calcite/recrystallised mineral in the pretreated sample. Is -9999.99 even if "PCT_RE_VAL" = 998
PCT_RE_MTD	varchar(5):P	Stain – Fiegl's stain XRD – X-ray diffractometry FTIR – FT infrared spectroscopy Micro – Microscopy Other – for other or ND – no data	ND	How was the presence and/or amount of calcite/recrystallisation measured in the pretreated carbonate sample
Age determination and sample activity data				
C14_AGE	numeric [BP]	[value] or -9999.99 – no data	145	Conventional radiocarbon age (CRA), as defined by Stuiver and Polach (1977): (1) the use of the Libby half-life value of 5568 years (mean life 8033 years); (2) the assumption of uniformity in ¹⁴ C activity throughout the biosphere in the past; (3) the use of oxalic acid or a secondary standard as the modern standard; (4) isotopic fractionation normalization of all sample activities to the base of δ ¹³ C = -25.0 per mille (relative to the ¹³ C: ¹² C ratio of PDB standard); and, (5) the use of AD 1950 as the base year, with ages given in years before present (BP) (i.e., AD 1950 = 0 BP) This definition may not be met prior to c.1980 and is unlikely to be met prior to 1977. If the database user wishes to use dates from this period, they will need to establish how the radiocarbon age was calculated.
C14_ERRPOS	numeric [BP]	[value] or -9999.99 – no data	20	Estimated standard error attached to an individual determination, equal to one standard deviation (1σ). Note that occasionally determinations have asymmetrical standard deviations.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
C14_ERRNEG	numeric [BP]	[value] or -9999.99 – no data	25	Estimated standard error attached to an individual determination, equal to one standard deviation (1σ). Note that occasionally determinations have asymmetrical standard deviations.
C14_INF	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	No	Is the date infinite (indistinguishable from the laboratory background). This field clarifies the two previous fields, where no data may be misinterpreted as an infinite measurement
F14C	numeric	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Proportion of radiocarbon atoms in the sample compared to that present in the year AD 1950. "F14C" is pMC (percent modern carbon)/100.
F14C_ERR	numeric	[value, two decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-9999.99	Error for proportion of radiocarbon atoms in the sample compared to that present in the year AD 1950. The error for "F14C" is the error for pMC (percent modern carbon)/100.
C13_VAL	int2:P	1 – Measured by AMS 2 – Measured by IRMS or CRDS 3 – Assumed or -9999 – no data	Measured by IRMS or CRDS	Was the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ used to calculate the age measured or assumed. If measured, how was it measured. Note that $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value on graphite is not included as it is not equivalent to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ on the pretreated material.
AGE_COMMT	text	[value] or NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Free text age comment field.

Table S5

Database field descriptions: SahulArch OSL

OCTOPUSdata/ Sahul Archaeology/ OSL collection. Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	[ARCH#####AAR###] – for AAR [ARCH#####C14###] – for C14 [ARCH#####CRD###] – for CRD [ARCH#####ESR###] – for ESR [ARCH#####OCR###] – for OCR [ARCH#####OSL###] – for OSL [ARCH#####TL###] – for TL [ARCH#####U###] – for U-series	ARCH0013OSL001	Unique age identifier provided as part of the compilation. The first part of the identifier (i.e., ARCH#####) is linked to “SITEID”, the ID of the site. The second part of the identifier is unique to the database entry and does also include abbreviation given to the method used to produce the age. For method abbreviations see “METHOD”.
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	OSL A	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample. Samples labelled only by numbers in the literature (e.g. 1, 2, 3 etc) have had a compound prefix – first three author name letters AND double-digit publication year – added (e.g. ‘Nan87_1’ for sample 1 (Nanson 1987)).
LABID	text	[value] or ND – no data	Shfd17118	Unique lab code assigned by the lab where age was determined. For radiocarbon (and for many luminescence) labs, the first part of the lab code refers to the determining facility.
LAB_FACLT	text:P	[value]	Sheffield Luminescence Lab.	Name of the laboratory where age was determined (where deducible from “LABID”)
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	10.25900/ypr0-j711	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[ARCH#####SMP###x]	ARCH0013SMP001a	Sample identifier provided as part of the compilation. The first part of the identifier (i.e., ARCH#####) is linked to “SITEID”, the ID of the site.

23.11.2022. DBVER 2022. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25900/9y07-4j77>. Data type: numeric(precision, scale), for non-numeric: (3) = field length; I = indexed, U = unique, NN = not nullable, P = predefined.

Data type description <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/13/datatype.html>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
				Where it is clear that two or more observations (dates/ rates) have been measured on one sample, they have the same "SMPID" but a different "OBSID1". This also applies across methods, e.g., one sample with an OSL age and an U-series age will have the same "SMPID" but different "OBSID1" (i.e. ARCH####OSL### and ARCH####U###).
SITEID	text:NN	[ARCH####x]	ARCH0001a	Unique site identifier provided as part of the compilation
METASITEID	text	[META_ARCH####]	META_ARCH0001	Unique metasite identifier provided as part of the compilation
METANAME	text	[value]	Madjedbebe	Metasite name
METHODABBR	text:P:NN	[methodid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Amino Acid Racemization (AAR) 2 – Radiocarbon Dating (C14) 3 – Cation Ratio Dating (CRD) 4 – Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) 5 – Oxidisable Carbon Ratio (OCR)	OSL 6 – Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) 7 – Thermoluminescence (TL) 8 – Uranium-Series (U)	9 – Closed-system U-Series and ESR model (CSU-ESR) 10 – Stratigraphic correlation (Strat) 11 – Coupled U-ESR model (U-ESR)
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	AUS TSI – Torres Strait Islands	Refers to Sahul region. Same as "CNTRY" but needed to accommodate for 'TSI' or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania	AU-WA PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
LAKE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of lake where study site is located
BASIN	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	Drysdale River	Name of river basin where study site is located

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		NA – for not applicable		
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS_07	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGLF1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Drysdale River	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Tanami-Timor Sea Coast	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	NOK	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Northern Kimberley	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	150.901171	WGS84 longitude of the site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i> <i>Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.</i>
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-34.414173	WGS84 latitude of the site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i> <i>Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.</i>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data	ORIG_INTP	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or ‘ORIG_’, or ‘ND_’). Second part of value refers to “ELEVATION” (‘_INTP’, or ‘_ORIG’, or ‘_ND’). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value] or -9999 – no data	39.2	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITENAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Minjiwarra	Name of the site
SITE_SPEC	text	[value] or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text field that allows for a brief description of the site
ALTNAME1	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	Big Red	First alternative or additional name of the site (e.g., published under previous name etc.)
ALTNAME2	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Second alternative or additional name of the site
ALTNAME3	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Third alternative or additional name of the site
SITECODE	text:P	[sitecodeid – value] 1 – Stone artefact deposit 2 – Burial (animal) 3 – Burial (human)	Open site 8 – Open site	Site type characterising the dominant attribute of the site. For example, burials in a rockshelter with lots of occupation deposit would be classified as a Rockshelter, not a Cemetery. 13 – Stone structure

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		4 – Cemetery 5 – Earth mound 6 – Hearth (isolated) 7 – Shell midden	9 – Quarry 10 – Rock art 11 – Rockshelter or cave 12 – Culturally modified tree	19 – Other or -9999 – no data (ND)
OPENCLOSED	varchar(6):P	Open Closed or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Open	This field records whether the site was closed (i.e., a rockshelter, cave or other enclosed site) or open (i.e., an artefact scatter, midden on a beach etc.), and is used in the application of taphonomic techniques in time-series analysis. Please note that 'Closed' does not relate to availability or accessibility of information.
SITE_COMMT	text	<i>[value]</i> or NA – for not applicable	Predicted to date to the Holocene; lighter and less cemented sediments	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	Veth:2019kimberley	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data	OAID-000403	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Veth	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR1	int2	<i>[YYYY]</i> – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2019	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	<i>[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol]</i> or	Aust_Archaeol_85 or second example	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e., PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130 Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1080/03122417.2019.1650479	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	[value] or <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable	Roberts	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
Sample provenance and characteristics				
FEATDATED	text:P	<i>[featdatedid – value]</i> 1 – Hearth 2 – Burial (animal) 3 – Burial (human)	not related to a feature 4 – Mud wasp nest 5 – Rock art 9 – Other	Specific feature dated, where applicable. or 999 – for not related to a feature -9999 – no data (ND)
SQUARE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Square or trench designation from where the sample is from.
XU	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	SU5	Excavation Unit (“XU”) or spit designation from where the sample is from.
SMPDEPTH	numeric(9,2) [m]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	2.80	Depth below the surface (or datum) from which sample was extracted. If the published sample depth was specified as a range, then the median value for that range is reported here.
SMPX_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	<i>[value; six decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	149.074222	WGS84 longitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>
SMPY_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	<i>[value; six decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-35.678042	WGS84 latitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>
OCCUPATION	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	No	Is the dated sample directly related to human activity (e.g., hearth, organic artefact, burial), or was it simply part of a wider archaeological deposit

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		NA – for not applicable		
CONTEXT	varchar(10):P	Occupation Sterile or ND – no data	ND	Was the sample collected from a stratigraphic unit that is associated with human 'Occupation' or one that was culturally 'Sterile'.
SMP_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text sample comment field.
COL_MTD	text:P	[col_mtdid – value] 1 – Auger 2 – Block 3 – Core 4 – Downhole Tube 5 – Excavated	Tube 6 – Tube 7 – Other 8 – InSitu	Sample collection method for OSL dating. 'InSitu' = plotted during excavation or removed from section. 9 – Sieve or -9999 – ND; for no data
LUM_MAT	text:P	[lum_matid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Burnt stone (Burnt) 2 – Cobbles (Cobble) 3 – Sediment (Sed) 4 – Rock surface (Surf)	Sediment 5 – Mud wasp nest (Wasp) 6 – for other (Other)	Type of sample material used for OSL and TL dating or -9999 – for no data (ND)
MINERAL	text:P	[mineralid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Calcite/Aragonite (Ca) 2 – Potassium Feldspar (KF) 3 – Sodium Feldspar (NaF)	Quartz 4 – Polym mineral (Poly) 5 – Quartz (Q)	Type of mineral used for equivalent dose determination or -9999 – for no data
SIZE_MIN	int2 [µm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	125	Reported minimum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination
SIZE_MAX	int2 [µm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	180	Reported maximum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
H2O_MEAS	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.80	Water content as measured from the sample. “H2O_MEAS” will be -9999.99 for estimated, but not measured water content. For those samples, “H2O_USED” will hold the reported estimated value. If the measured water content is given as <1% in the original publication, then 1.0 was recorded here.
H2O_USED	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.80	Water content used for environmental dose rate determination
H2O_ERR	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	3.00	Standard error for “H2O_USED” (1σ)
Equivalent dose measurements				
OSL_TYPEAB	text:P	[osl_typeid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Infrared Stimulated Lum. (IRSL) 2 – Multiple Elevated Temperature post-Infrared IRSL (MET-pIRIR) 3 – Optically Stimulated Lum. (OSL)	OSL 4 – Post-Infrared IRSL; 2-step (pIRIR) 5 – Thermally Transferred OSL (TT-OSL) 6 – Violet Stimulated Lum. (VSL)	Abbreviated published Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL) type used to determine equivalent dose 7 – for undefined OSL type (Other) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
ALIQ_TYPE	varchar(3):P	SG – Single Grain SA – Single Aliquot MA – Multiple Aliquots or ND – for no data	SA	Reported aliquot type used for equivalent dose determination
ALIQ_SIZE	numeric [mm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	-9999.99	Reported size of aliquot diameter in mm
ED_PROCABR	text:P	[ed_procid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – ‘Australian Slide’ (AS) 2 – Combined Regenerative and Additive Method (CRAM)	SAR 4 – Multiple Aliquot Regenerative Dose (MAR)	Abbreviated reported procedure used to determine sample equivalent dose for OSL and TL methods 6 – Single Aliquot Additive Dose (SAAD) or

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		3 – Multiple Aliquot Additive Dose (MAAD)	5 – Single Aliquot Regenerative Dose (SAR)	-9999 – for no data (ND)
RESCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Residual dose correction was applied to the Equivalent Dose, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, MET-pIRIR, VSL, and TT-OSL
DOSERECOV	varchar(3):P	Yes No or NA – not applicable ND – for no data	Yes	Were dose recovery test results reported in the study?
AGEMODELAB	text:P	<i>[agemodelid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Average Dose Model (ADM) 2 – Arithmetic Mean (AVG) 3 – Average variance (AVVAR) 4 – Central Age Model (CAM) 5 – Unlogged Central Age Model (CAM_UL) 6 – Common Age Model (COM_AM) 7 – Finite Mixture Model (FMM)	CAM 8 – Internal–External Consistency Criterion (IEU) 9 – Minimum Age Model (MAM) 10 – Unlogged Minimum Age Model (MAM_UL) 11 – Maximum Age Model (MAX)	Abbreviated model used to combine individual equivalent dose estimates for age determination 12 – normalised Median Absolute Deviation Central Age Model (nMAD_CAM) 13 – pdf Gaussian Age Model (PDFG) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
PH1_TEMP	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	240	Preheat temperature applied immediately prior to measurement of either the Natural, Regenerative or Additive dose
PH2_TEMP	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	-9999	Preheat temperature applied immediately prior to measurement of test dose
NUM_MEAS	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	-9999	Number of aliquots/grains measured for the sample
NUM_ACC	int2 [°C]	<i>[value]</i>	-9999	Number of aliquots/grains accepted for equivalent dose determination

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or -9999 – for no data		
EQUIVDOSE	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	9.85	Reported equivalent dose in Gy, sometimes referred to as ED, D _e , palaeodose (P) or burial dose
ED_ERR	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.11	Published error for the equivalent dose at 1 standard error (1σ)
ED_INF	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Natural signal projected onto the dose saturation plateau of dose response curve (D _e represented is a minimum value)
OD	numeric	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	5.00	Overdispersion value for equivalent dose dataset calculated as per Galbraith <i>et al.</i> , (1999)
OD_ERR	numeric	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Overdispersion error value (at 1 standard error, 1σ) for equivalent dose data set calculated as per Galbraith <i>et al.</i> , (1999)
OD_TYPE	varchar(3):P	% – Percentage Gy – Gray or ND – for no data	%	The unit of measure for “OD” and “OD_ERR” values
Radionuclide concentrations				
U	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	1.68	Uranium content of the sample
U_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the uranium content of the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
U_MTDAB	text:P	<p><i>[u_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i></p> <p>1 – Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS)</p> <p>2 – Flame Photometry (F)</p> <p>3 – In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (FGS)</p> <p>4 – Combined In-situ Gamma Spectrometry and Neutron Activation Analysis (FGS+NAA)</p> <p>5 – Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (GMBC)</p> <p>6 – combined GMBC and FGS results (GMBC+FGS)</p> <p>7 – High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)</p> <p>8 – Combined High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS&FGS)</p> <p>9 – Combined HRGS and High-resolution alpha-spectrometry (HRGS&HRAS)</p> <p>10 – Mean of HRGS and XRF (HRGS&XRF)</p> <p>11 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-A/OES)</p> <p>12 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS)</p>	ICP-MS	<p>Abbreviated method used to determine uranium content of the sample in data field “U”.</p> <p>Note 1 – NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA.</p> <p>Note 2 – lookup table behind “U_MTDAB” serves other fields/methods too, i.e., is not exclusively serving “U”</p> <p>13 – Combined ICP-MS and –A/OES results (ICP-MS+ICP-A/OES)</p> <p>14 – Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA)</p> <p>15 – Combined NAA and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry results (NAA+FGS)</p> <p>16 – Mean of NAA and HRGS (NAA+HRGS)</p> <p>17 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (NAA+ICP-MS)</p> <p>18 – Neutron Activation Analysis (+Potassium) (NAA+K)</p> <p>19 – Mean of NAA and TSAC (NAA+TSAC)</p> <p>20 – Mean of NAA and XRF (NAA+XRF)</p> <p>21 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (TSAC)</p> <p>22 – Thick Source Alpha Counting + Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (TSAC+GMBC)</p> <p>23 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (+Potassium) (TSAC+K)</p> <p>24 – X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)</p> <p>25 – Other (Other)</p> <p>26 – TBA (DNA+TSAC)</p> <p>27 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (NAA+ICP-A/OES)</p> <p>28 – Combined X-ray Fluorescence and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (XRF+ICP-A/OES)</p> <p>29 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (+Potassium) (NAA+ICP-MS+K)</p> <p>31 – Flame Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (F-AES)</p> <p>32 – Combined AES and XRF results (AES+XRF)</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999 – no data (ND)</p> <p>-9991 – not applicable (NA)</p>
TH	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	<p><i>[value; two decimal places]</i></p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999.99 – for no data</p>	4.40	Thorium content of the sample
TH_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	<p><i>[value; two decimal places]</i></p> <p>or</p> <p>-9999.99 – for no data</p>	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the thorium content of the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
TH_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[th_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ICP-MS	Method used to determine thorium content of the sample in data field “TH”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
K	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.40	Potassium content of the sample. N.B. K not K ₂ O
K_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the potassium content of the sample
K_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[k_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ICP-A/OES	Method used to determine potassium content of the sample in data field “K”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
High Resolution Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS) activities				
U238	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³⁸ U content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
U238_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “U238”
RA226	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁶ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA226_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA226”
PB210	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²¹⁰ Pb content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
PB210_ERR	numeric	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	-9999.99	Published error value for “PB210”

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
	[Bq/kg]	or -9999.99 – for no data		
RA228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA228”
TH228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH228”
TH232	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³² Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH232_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH232”
K40	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	⁴⁰ K content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
K40_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “K40”
External dose rate measurements				
ALPH	numeric	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	-9999.99	External alpha dose rate (wet)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
	[Gy/ka]	or -9999.99 – for no data		
ALPH_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external alpha dose rate
ALPH_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[alph_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	NA	Abbreviated method used to determine external alpha dose rate. If study authors have specified that the grains were HF etched, then “ALPH_MTD” will be ‘NA’ (due to the alpha-irradiated surface of the grains being removed). <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
BETA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External beta dose rate (wet)
BETA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external beta dose rate
BETA_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[beta_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine external beta dose rate <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
GAMMA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External gamma dose rate (wet)
GAMMA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external gamma dose rate
GAMMA_MTDA	text:P	<i>[gamma_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Method used to determine external gamma dose rate Note that the NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA.
COSMIC	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	0.14	Cosmic dose rate (wet)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or -9999.99 – for no data		
COSMIC_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.01	1 standard error (1 σ) for cosmic dose rate
Internal dose rate measurements				
ALPH_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal alpha dose rate (from within grain)
ALPH_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1 σ) for internal alpha dose rate
ALPH_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal alpha dose rate assumed or measured?
BETA_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal beta dose rate (from within grain)
BETA_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1 σ) for internal beta dose rate
BETA_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal beta dose rate assumed or measured?
DIFF_DOSE	varchar(3):P	Yes No or	No	Whether a different and/or additional method, not specified in this compilation was used to determine the dosimetry for this sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		ND – for no data		
Total dose rate				
DOSERATE	numeric [Gy/ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	1.278	Total (wet) environmental dose rate used for age determination
DOSE_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.049	Total (wet) environmental dose rate error at 1σ
Age determination				
OSL_AGE	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	7.70	Published OSL age
OSL_RNDERR	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published Random only “OSL_AGE” error
OSL_ERR	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.30	Published total “OSL_AGE” error (random + systematic)
AGE_CI	varchar(3):P	1s – 1 standard error [1σ] 2s – 2 standard error [2σ] SD – Standard Deviation or ND – for no data	1s	Published confidence interval on the age estimate
FADCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	ND	“OSL_AGE” was corrected for fading, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, and MET-pIRIR

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
G_VAL	numeric [%/10a]	<i>[value; one decimal place]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Represents the correcting approach using value of fading rate in feldspars. If reported, express as percent per decade.
G_VAL_ERR	numeric [%/10a]	<i>[value; one decimal place]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published 1 σ error for the “G_VAL”
AGE_COMMT	text	<i>[value]</i> or <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable	<i>NULL</i>	Free text age comment field.

Table S6

Database field descriptions: SahulArch TL

OCTOPUSdata/ Sahul Archaeology/ TL collection. Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	[ARCH#####AAR###] – for AAR [ARCH#####C14###] – for C14 [ARCH#####CRD###] – for CRD [ARCH#####ESR###] – for ESR [ARCH#####OCR###] – for OCR [ARCH#####OSL###] – for OSL [ARCH#####TL###] – for TL [ARCH#####U###] – for U-series	ARCH0015TL001	Unique age identifier provided as part of the compilation. The first part of the identifier (i.e., ARCH#####) is linked to “SITEID”, the ID of the site. The second part of the identifier is unique to the database entry and does also include abbreviation given to the method used to produce the age. For method abbreviations see “METHOD”.
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	C/U2	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample. Samples labelled only by numbers in the literature (e.g. 1, 2, 3 etc) have had a compound prefix – first three author name letters AND double-digit publication year – added (e.g. ‘Nan87_1’ for sample 1 (Nanson 1987)).
LABID	text	[value] or ND – no data	W1424	Unique lab code assigned by the lab where age was determined. For radiocarbon (and for many luminescence) labs, the first part of the lab code refers to the determining facility.
LAB_FACLT	text:P	[value]	UOW TL Dating Lab. Wollongong	Name of the laboratory where age was determined (where deducible from “LABID”)
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	10.25900/xq40-t003	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[ARCH#####SMP###x]	ARCH0015SMP001a	Sample identifier provided as part of the compilation.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
				The first part of the identifier (i.e., <i>ARCH####</i>) is linked to “SITEID”, the ID of the site. Where it is clear that two or more observations (dates/ rates) have been measured on one sample, they have the same “SMPID” but a different “OBSID1”. This also applies across methods, e.g., one sample with an OSL age and an U-series age will have the same “SMPID” but different “OBSID1” (i.e. <i>ARCH####OSL###</i> and <i>ARCH####U####</i>).
SITEID	text:NN	[<i>ARCH####x</i>]	ARCH0001a	Unique site identifier provided as part of the compilation
METASITEID	text	[<i>META_ARCH####</i>]	META_ARCH0001	Unique metasite identifier provided as part of the compilation
METANAME	text	[<i>value</i>]	Madjedbebe	Metasite name
METHODABBR	text:P:NN	[<i>methodid – value (abbreviation)</i>] 1 – Amino Acid Racemization (AAR) 2 – Radiocarbon Dating (C14) 3 – Cation Ratio Dating (CRD) 4 – Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)	TL	Abbreviated type of method used in age determination 5 – Oxidisable Carbon Ratio (OCR) 6 – Optically Stimulated Lum. (OSL) 7 – Thermoluminescence (TL) 8 – Uranium-Series (U) 9 – Closed-system U-Series and ESR model (CSU-ESR) 10 – Stratigraphic correlation (Strat) 11 – Coupled U-ESR model (U-ESR)
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[<i>value</i>] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[<i>value</i>] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	AUS TSI – Torres Strait Islands	Refers to Sahul region. Same as “CNTRY” but needed to accommodate for ‘TSI’ or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia	AU-NT PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		AU-TAS – Tasmania AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	PG-EBR – East New Britain PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
LAKE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of lake where study site is located
BASIN	text	<i>[value]</i> or	Keep River	Name of river basin where study site is located

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		ND – no data NA – for not applicable		
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TTS_09	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGLF1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Keep River	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Tanami-Timor Sea Coast	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	VIB	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Victoria Bonaparte	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	150.901171	WGS84 longitude of the site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i> <i>Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.</i>
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-34.414173	WGS84 latitude of the site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i> <i>Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.</i>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data	INTP_INTP	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or ‘ORIG_’, or ‘ND_’). Second part of value refers to “ELEVATION” (‘_INTP’, or ‘_ORIG’, or ‘_ND’). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value] or -9999 – no data	46	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITENAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Jinmium	Name of the site
SITE_SPEC	text	[value] or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text field that allows for a brief description of the site
ALTNAME1	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	First alternative or additional name of the site (e.g., published under previous name etc.)
ALTNAME2	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Second alternative or additional name of the site
ALTNAME3	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Third alternative or additional name of the site
SITECODE	text:P	[sitecodeid – value] 1 – Stone artefact deposit 2 – Burial (animal) 3 – Burial (human)	Rockshelter or cave 8 – Open site	Site type characterising the dominant attribute of the site. For example, burials in a rockshelter with lots of occupation deposit would be classified as a Rockshelter, not a Cemetery. 13 – Stone structure

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		4 – Cemetery 5 – Earth mound 6 – Hearth (isolated) 7 – Shell midden	9 – Quarry 10 – Rock art 11 – Rockshelter or cave 12 – Culturally modified tree	19 – Other or -9999 – no data (ND)
OPENCLOSED	varchar(6):P	Open Closed or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Closed	This field records whether the site was closed (i.e., a rockshelter, cave or other enclosed site) or open (i.e., an artefact scatter, midden on a beach etc.), and is used in the application of taphonomic techniques in time-series analysis. Please note that 'Closed' does not relate to availability or accessibility of information.
SITE_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	[value] or ND – no data	Fullagar:1996jinmium	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	[value] or ND – no data	OAID-000258	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Fullagar	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR1	int2	[YYYY] – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	1996	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol] or	Antiquity_70 or second example	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e., PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130 Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1017/S0003598X00084040	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	[value] or <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable	Roberts	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples and Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
Sample provenance and characteristics				
FEATDATED	text:P	<i>[featdatedid – value]</i> 1 – Hearth 2 – Burial (animal) 3 – Burial (human)	not related to a feature 4 – Mud wasp nest 5 – Rock art 9 – Other	Specific feature dated, where applicable. or 999 – for not related to a feature -9999 – no data (ND)
SQUARE	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	C1	Square or trench designation from where the sample is from.
XU	text	<i>[value]</i> or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Unit 1	Excavation Unit (“XU”) or spit designation from where the sample is from.
SMPDEPTH	numeric(9,2) [m]	<i>[value, two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	0.95	Depth below the surface (or datum) from which sample was extracted. If the published sample depth was specified as a range, then the median value for that range is reported here.
SMPX_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	<i>[value; six decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	149.074222	WGS84 longitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>
SMPY_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	<i>[value; six decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – no data	-35.678042	WGS84 latitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>
OCCUPATION	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – no data	No	Is the dated sample directly related to human activity (e.g. hearth, organic artefact, burial), or was it simply part of a wider archaeological deposit

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		NA – for not applicable		
CONTEXT	varchar(10):P	Occupation Sterile or ND – no data	ND	Was the sample collected from a stratigraphic unit that is associated with human 'Occupation' or one that was culturally 'Sterile'.
SMP_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text sample comment field.
COL_MTD	text:P	[col_mtdid – value] 1 – Auger 2 – Block 3 – Core 4 – Downhole Tube 5 – Excavated	Tube 6 – Tube 7 – Other 8 – InSitu	Sample collection method for TL dating. 'InSitu' = plotted during excavation or removed from section. 9 – Sieve or -9999 – ND; for no data
LUM_MAT	text:P	[lum_matid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Burnt stone (Burnt) 2 – Cobbles (Cobble) 3 – Sediment (Sed) 4 – Rock surface (Surf)	Sediment 5 – Mud wasp nest (Wasp) 6 – for other (Other)	Type of sample material used for OSL and TL dating or -9999 – for no data (ND)
MINERAL	text:P	[mineralid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Calcite/Aragonite (Ca) 2 – Potassium Feldspar (KF) 3 – Sodium Feldspar (NaF)	Quartz 4 – Polym mineral (Poly) 5 – Quartz (Q)	Type of mineral used for equivalent dose determination or -9999 – for no data
SIZE_MIN	int2 [µm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	90	Reported minimum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination
SIZE_MAX	int2 [µm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	125	Reported maximum grain size used for equivalent dose and environmental dose rate determination

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
H2O_MEAS	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Water content as measured from the sample. “H2O_MEAS” will be -9999.99 for estimated, but not measured water content. For those samples, “H2O_USED” will hold the reported estimated value. If the measured water content is given as <1% in the original publication, then 1.0 was recorded here.
H2O_USED	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.50	Water content used for environmental dose rate determination
H2O_ERR	numeric [%]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	3.00	Standard error for “H2O_USED” (1σ)
Equivalent dose measurements				
ALIQ_SIZE	numeric [mm]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	-9999.99	Reported size of aliquot diameter in mm
ED_PROCABR	text:P	[ed_procid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – ‘Australian Slide’ (AS) 2 – Combined Regenerative and Additive Method (CRAM) 3 – Multiple Aliquot Additive Dose (MAAD)	CRAM 4 – Multiple Aliquot Regenerative Dose (MAR) 5 – Single Aliquot Regenerative Dose (SAR)	Abbreviated reported procedure used to determine sample equivalent dose for OSL and TL methods 6 – Single Aliquot Additive Dose (SAAD) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
RESCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	ND	Residual dose correction was applied to the Equivalent Dose, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, MET-pIRIR, VSL, and TT-OSL
AGEMODELAB	text:P	[agemodelid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Average Dose Model (ADM) 2 – Arithmetic Mean (AVG) 3 – Average variance (AVVAR) 4 – Central Age Model (CAM)	AVG 8 – Internal–External Consistency Criterion (IEU)	Abbreviated model used to combine individual equivalent dose estimates for age determination 12 – normalised Median Absolute Deviation Central Age Model (nMAD_CAM)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		5 – Unlogged Central Age Model (CAM_UL) 6 – Common Age Model (COM_AM) 7 – Finite Mixture Model (FMM)	9 – Minimum Age Model (MAM) 10 – Unlogged Minimum Age Model (MAM_UL) 11 – Maximum Age Model (MAX)	13 – pdf Gaussian Age Model (PDFG) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
PLAT_REG	varchar(9) [°C]	[range] or ND – for no data	375-500	Pre-heat plateau region
AN_TEMP	int2 [°C]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	375	Specific temperature at which analysis is performed
NUM_MEAS	int2 [°C]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	28	Number of aliquots/grains measured for the sample
EQUIVDOSE	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	48.9	Reported equivalent dose in Gy, sometimes referred to as ED, D _e , palaeodose (P) or burial dose
ED_ERR	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	5	Published error for the equivalent dose at 1 standard error (1σ)
ED_SAT	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Equivalent dose (ED) for the saturated age
ED_SATERR	numeric [Gy]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published 1σ error for the saturated age
Radionuclide concentrations				
U	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Uranium content of the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
U_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the uranium content of the sample
U_MTDAB	text:P	[u_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) 2 – Flame Photometry (F) 3 – In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (FGS) 4 – Combined In-situ Gamma Spectrometry and Neutron Activation Analysis (FGS+NAA) 5 – Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (GMBC) 6 – combined GMBC and FGS results (GMBC+FGS) 7 – High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS) 8 – Combined High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS&FGS) 9 – Combined HRGS and High-resolution alpha-spectrometry (HRGS&HRAS) 10 – Mean of HRGS and XRF (HRGS&XRF) 11 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-A/OES) 12 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) 13 – Combined ICP-MS and –A/OES results (ICP-MS+ICP-A/OES) 14 – Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA) 15 – Combined NAA and In-situ Gamma Spectrometry results (NAA+FGS) 16 – Mean of NAA and HRGS (NAA+HRGS) 17 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (NAA+ICP-MS) 18 – Neutron Activation Analysis (+Potassium) (NAA+K) 19 – Mean of NAA and TSAC (NAA+TSAC) 20 – Mean of NAA and XRF (NAA+XRF) 21 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (TSAC) 22 – Thick Source Alpha Counting + Geiger-Müller Beta Counting (TSAC+GMBC) 23 – Thick Source Alpha Counting (+Potassium) (TSAC+K) 24 – X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) 25 – Other (Other) 26 – TBA (DNA+TSAC) 27 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (NAA+ICP-A/OES) 28 – Combined X-ray Fluorescence and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic or Optical Emission Spectroscopy (XRF+ICP-A/OES) 29 – Combined Neutron Activation Analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (+Potassium) (NAA+ICP-MS+K) 31 – Flame Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (F-AES) 32 – Combined AES and XRF results (AES+XRF) or -9999 – no data (ND) -9991 – not applicable (NA)	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine uranium content of the sample in data field “U”. Note 1 – NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA. Note 2 – lookup table behind “U_MTDAB” serves other fields/methods too, i.e., is not exclusively serving “U”
TH	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Thorium content of the sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
TH_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Standard error (1σ) for the thorium content of the sample
TH_MTDAB	text:P	[th_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Method used to determine thorium content of the sample in data field “TH”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
U_TH	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	29.8	When U and Th elemental content are reported together, rather than separate U and Th. Reported as radioactive element specific activity
U_TH_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.90	Published error for “U_TH” specific activity
U_TH_MTD	text:P	[u_th_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	TSAC	Method used to determine “U_TH” specific activity of the sample in the field “U_TH” <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
K	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0.08	Potassium content of the sample. N.B. K not K ₂ O
K_ERR	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value; two decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	0	Standard error (1σ) for the potassium content of the sample
K_MTDAB	text:P	k_mtdid – value (abbreviation)] Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	AAS	Method used to determine potassium content of the sample in data field “K”. <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
RB	numeric [ppm / µg/g]	[value] or -9999.99 – for no data	10	Rubidium (Rb) content

High Resolution Gamma Spectrometry (HRGS) activities

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
U238	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³⁸ U content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
U238_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “U238”
RA226	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁶ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA226_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA226”
PB210	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²¹⁰ Pb content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
PB210_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “PB210”
RA228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Ra content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
RA228_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “RA228”
TH228	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²²⁸ Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH228_ERR	numeric	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i>	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH228”

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
	[Bq/kg]	or -9999.99 – for no data		
TH232	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	²³² Th content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
TH232_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “TH232”
K40	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	⁴⁰ K content from High-Resolution Gamma-ray Spectrometry (HRGS)
K40_ERR	numeric [Bq/kg]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published error value for “K40”
External dose rate measurements				
ALPH	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External alpha dose rate (wet)
ALPH_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external alpha dose rate
ALPH_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[alph_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine external alpha dose rate. If study authors have specified that the grains were HF etched, then “ALPH_MTD” will be ‘NA’ (due to the alpha-irradiated surface of the grains being removed). <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
BETA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External beta dose rate (wet)

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
BETA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external beta dose rate
BETA_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[beta_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Abbreviated method used to determine external beta dose rate <i>Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values and description!</i>
GAMMA	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	External gamma dose rate (wet)
GAMMA_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for external gamma dose rate
GAMMA_MTDAB	text:P	<i>[gamma_mtdid – value (abbreviation)]</i> Refer to “U_MTDAB” for values!	ND	Method used to determine external gamma dose rate Note that the NAA term covers any NAA-based methodology as for instance INAA or DNAA.
COSMIC	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.15	Cosmic dose rate (wet)
COSMIC_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for cosmic dose rate
Internal dose rate measurements				
ALPH_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal alpha dose rate (from within grain)
ALPH_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1σ) for internal alpha dose rate

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
ALPH_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal alpha dose rate assumed or measured?
BETA_I	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Internal beta dose rate (from within grain)
BETA_I_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	1 standard error (1 σ) for internal beta dose rate
BETA_I_MTD	varchar(8):P	Assumed Measured or ND – for no data	ND	Was the internal beta dose rate assumed or measured?
DIFF_DOSE	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data	No	Whether a different and/or additional method, not specified in this compilation was used to determine the dosimetry for this sample
Total dose rate				
DOSERATE	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.844	Total (wet) environmental dose rate used for age determination
DOSE_ERR	numeric [Gy/ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	0.052	Total (wet) environmental dose rate error at 1 σ
Age determination				
TL_AGE	numeric [ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	58.00	Published TL age

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
TL_RNDERR	numeric [ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published Random only “TL_AGE” error
TL_ERR	numeric [ka]	<i>[value; three decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	6.90	Published total “TL_AGE” error (random + systematic)
AGE_CI	varchar(3):P	1s – 1 standard error [1σ] 2s – 2 standard error [2σ] SD – Standard Deviation or ND – for no data	1s	Published confidence interval on the age estimate
FADCOR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	ND	“TL_AGE” was corrected for fading, specifically for IRSL, pIRIR, and MET-pIRIR
G_VAL	numeric [%/10a]	<i>[value; one decimal place]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Represents the correcting approach using value of fading rate in feldspars. If reported, express as percent per decade.
G_VAL_ERR	numeric [%/10a]	<i>[value; one decimal place]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Published 1σ error for the “G_VAL”
AGE_COMMT	text	<i>[value]</i> or NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Free text age comment field.

Table S7

Database field descriptions: ExpAge

OCTOPUSdata/ Expage global collection of apparent boulder exposure ages. Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Observation information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	[AuthYear-SampleNo<x>]	Augu2017-17a	Unique age identifier provided as part of the compilation. Serves as back reference to parent expage fork (https://expage.github.io), with running alphabetic letter(s) added to the original "Sample ID".
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	BV-WC-44	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample.
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	no_DOI_available	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[OBSID1<.xxx>]	Augu2017-17.boc	Unique sample identifier that serves database operation.
SITEID	text:NN	[OBSID1<-X.x>]	Augu2017-17-F.f	Unique site identifier that, first and foremost, serves database operation. Expage SITEIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated roundup (2) "X_WGS84" AND "METASITEID" AND roundup (2) "Y_WGS84", with running alphabetic letter(s) added.
METASITEID	text	[OBSID1<-X>]	Augu2017-17-F	Equals "GROUPLD" from parent expage fork (https://expage.github.io), i.e., is identifier to keep track of groups of samples derived from single sites with one deglaciation age.
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value]	Boco Creek Forest Reserve	Region where the study site is located

23.11.2022. DBVER 2021. Data type: numeric(precision, scale), for non-numeric: (3) = field length; I = indexed, U = unique, NN = not nullable, P = predefined.

Data type description <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/13/datatype.html>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or ND – no data NA – for not applicable		
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia	AUS	Refers to Sahul region. Same as “CNTRY” but needed to accommodate for ‘TSI’
		PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	TSI – Torres Strait Islands	or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland	AU-TAS	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located
		AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	PG-NSB – Bougainville TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region	NA	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located
		PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	or ND – no data NA – for not applicable

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
ISL_NAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Tasmania	Name of island where study site is located
BASIN	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Pieman River	Name of river basin where study site is located
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TAS	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TAS_10	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGFL1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Pieman River	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadatas/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Tasmania	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	TWE	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Tasmanian West	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	145.578066	WGS84 longitude of the site
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-41.707699	WGS84 latitude of the site
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data	ORIG_ND	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or ‘ORIG_’, or ‘ND_’). Second part of value refers to “ELEVATION” (‘_INTP’, or ‘_ORIG’, or ‘_ND’). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999 – no data	370	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITE_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	[value] or ND – no data	Augustinus:2017boco	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	[value] or ND – no data	OAID-000531	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Augustinus	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
PUBYEAR1	int2	[YYYY] – Year or 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2017	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol] or Book Book_Chapter	Quaternary_Sci_Rev_160 or second example Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e. PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html
		PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	Pers_Comm or ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	[value] – where available or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1016/j.quascirev.2017.01.015	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	[value] or NULL – for not applicable	NULL	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible Values, Examples and Description. NULL – for not applicable		

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
Type and shielding of material sampled				
MATERIAL	text	<i>[grnsizeid – value] (selection only)</i> 1 – Sand (Sa) 2 – Silt (Si) 3 – Clay (Cl) 4 – Large boulder (LBo) 5 – Boulder (Bo) 6 – Cobble (Co) 7 – Gravel (Gr) 71 – Coarse gravel (CGr) 72 – Medium gravel (MGr) 73 – Fine gravel (FGr) 31 – Coarse sand (CSa)	Boulder 32 – Medium sand (MSa) 33 – Fine sand (FSa) 21 – Coarse silt (CSi) 22 – Medium silt (MSi) 23 – Fine silt (FSi) 50 – Pebble (Pe) 12 – Silty Sand (SiSa) 13 – Clayey Sand (ClSa) 14 – Mix of Sand and Large boulder (SaLBo)	Type of material sampled 15 – Mix of Sand and Boulder (SaBo) 16 – Mix of Sand and Cobble (SaCo) 17 – Mix of Sand and Gravel (SaGr) 56 – Mix of Boulders and Cobbles (BoCo) 65 – Mix of Cobbles and Boulders (CoBo) 80 – Sediment (unspecified) (Sed) 81 – Loam (Lo) 100 – Bedrock (Bed) or -9999 – for no data (ND)
THICKNESS	numeric(7,4) [cm]	<i>[value]</i>	3.00	Sample thickness
DENSITY	numeric(6,4) [g.cm ⁻³]	<i>[value]</i>	2.70	Sample density. When information is not provided in original publication, 2.65 g cm ⁻³ is assumed
SHIELDING	numeric(7,6)	<i>[value]</i>	1	Topographic / geometric shielding of the sample
SMP_YR	int2	<i>[value]</i>	2015	Year of sample collection. Generally assumed to be two years before publication if not indicated.
SMP_COMMT	text	<i>[value]</i>	Topographic shielding set to 1 ('Shielding [---] was ?0.999 for all	Free text sample comment field.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
			samples'). Sampling year assumed to be 2015. Group ID based on publication (Table 2).	
Cosmogenic Be-10 data				
BE10NP	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	1776000	Published Be-10 concentration
BE10NP_ERR	int8 [atoms.g ⁻¹]	[value] or -9999 – for no data	86000	Published 1-sigma uncertainty in Be-10 concentration
BESTND	text:p	<p>[bestndid – stnd used (stnd published)]</p> <p>1 – 07KNSTD (07KNSTD) 2 – 07KNSTD (07KNSTD-Assumed) 3 – 07KNSTD (07KNSTD3110) 4 – 07KNSTD (07KNSTD3110-Assumed) 5 – BEST433 (BEST433) 6 – BEST433 (BEST433-Assumed)</p> <p>7 – BEST433N (BEST433N) 8 – BEST433N (BEST433N-Assumed) 9 – 07KNSTD (ICN) 10 – 07KNSTD (ICN-Assumed) 11 – 07KNSTD (ICN 01-5-2) 12 – 07KNSTD (ICN 01-5-2-Assumed) 13 – 07KNSTD (KN01-6-2) 14 – 07KNSTD (KN01-6-2-Assumed) 15 – KNSTD (KNSTD) 16 – KNSTD (KNSTD-Assumed) 17 – 07KNSTD (KNSTD3110) 18 – 07KNSTD (KNSTD3110-Assumed) 19 – LLNL1000 (LLNL1000) 20 – LLNL1000 (LLNL1000-Assumed) 21 – LLNL10000 (LLNL10000) 22 – LLNL10000 (LLNL10000-Assumed) 23 – LLNL300 (LLNL300)</p>	<p>07KNSTD</p> <p>28 – LLNL31000 (LLNL31000-Assumed) 29 – 07KNSTD (NIST SRM-4325) 30 – 07KNSTD (NIST SRM-4325-Assumed) 31 – 07KNSTD (NIST_27900) 32 – 07KNSTD (NIST_27900-Assumed) 33 – NIST_30000 (NIST_30000) 34 – NIST_30000 (NIST_30000-Assumed) 35 – NIST_30200 (NIST_30200) 36 – NIST_30200 (NIST_30200-Assumed) 37 – NIST_30300 (NIST_30300) 38 – NIST_30300 (NIST_30300-Assumed) 39 – NIST_30600 (NIST_30600)</p>	<p>Name of AMS Be standardisation used. When information is not provided (would be 'no data'), it is assumed that authors used the KNSTD standardisation as this is was the most commonly used standardisation prior to 2007 at AMS labs in the United States. Standards where 'stnd used' == '07KNSTD', for the sake of simplicity, are treated as 07KNSTD regardless of 'stnd published'.</p> <p>43 – S2007 (S2007) 44 – S2007 (S2007-Assumed) 45 – S2007N (S2007N) 46 – S2007N (S2007N-Assumed) 47 – S555 (S555) 48 – S555 (S555-Assumed) 49 – S555N (S555N) 50 – S555N (S555N-Assumed) 51 – 07KNSTD (SMD-Be-12) 52 – 07KNSTD (SMD-Be-12-Assumed) 53 – 07KNSTD (SRM KN-5-2) 54 – 07KNSTD (SRM KN-5-2-Assumed) 55 – 07KNSTD (STD-11) 56 – 07KNSTD (STD-11-Assumed) 57 – NIST_30500 (NIST_30500) 58 – NIST_30500 (NIST_30500-Assumed)</p>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		24 – LLNL300 (LLNL300-Assumed) 25 – LLNL3000 (LLNL3000) 26 – LLNL3000 (LLNL3000-Assumed) 27 – LLNL31000 (LLNL31000)	40 – NIST_30600 (NIST_30600-Assumed) 41 – NIST_Certified (NIST_Certified) 42 – NIST_Certified (NIST_Certified-Assumed)	or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
BECORR	numeric(5,4)	<i>[bestndid – becorr (stnd published)]</i> 1 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD) 2 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD-Assumed) 3 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD3110) 4 – 1.0000 (07KNSTD3110-Assumed) 5 – 0.9124 (BEST433) 6 – 0.9124 (BEST433-Assumed) 7 – 1.0000 (BEST433N) 8 – 1.0000 (BEST433N-Assumed) 9 – 1.0000 (ICN) 10 – 1.0000 (ICN-Assumed) 11 – 1.0000 (ICN 01-5-2) 12 – 1.0000 (ICN 01-5-2-Assumed) 13 – 1.0000 (KN01-6-2) 14 – 1.0000 (KN01-6-2-Assumed) 15 – 0.9042 (KNSTD) 16 – 0.9042 (KNSTD-Assumed) 17 – 1.0000 (KNSTD3110) 18 – 1.0000 (KNSTD3110-Assumed) 19 – 0.9313 (LLNL1000) 20 – 0.9313 (LLNL1000-Assumed) 21 – 0.9042 (LLNL10000) 22 – 0.9042 (LLNL10000-Assumed)	1.0000 23 – 0.8562 (LLNL300) 24 – 0.8562 (LLNL300-Assumed) 25 – 0.8644 (LLNL3000) 26 – 0.8644 (LLNL3000-Assumed) 27 – 0.8761 (LLNL31000) 28 – 0.8761 (LLNL31000-Assumed) 29 – 1.0000 (NIST SRM-4325) 30 – 1.0000 (NIST SRM-4325-Assumed) 31 – 1.0000 (NIST_27900) 32 – 1.0000 (NIST_27900-Assumed) 33 – 0.9313 (NIST_30000) 34 – 0.9313 (NIST_30000-Assumed) 35 – 0.9251 (NIST_30200) 36 – 0.9251 (NIST_30200-Assumed) 37 – 0.9221 (NIST_30300) 38 – 0.9221 (NIST_30300-Assumed) 39 – 0.9130 (NIST_30600) 40 – 0.9130 (NIST_30600-Assumed) 41 – 1.0425 (NIST_Certified)	Correction factor for a certain standardization that, multiplied with determined Be-10 concentration, will yield a nuclide concentration that is consistent with 07KNSTD 42 – 1.0425 (NIST_Certified-Assumed) 43 – 0.9124 (S2007) 44 – 0.9124 (S2007-Assumed) 45 – 1.0000 (S2007N) 46 – 1.0000 (S2007N-Assumed) 47 – 0.9124 (S555) 48 – 0.9124 (S555-Assumed) 49 – 1.0000 (S555N) 50 – 1.0000 (S555N-Assumed) 51 – 1.0000 (SMD-Be-12) 52 – 1.0000 (SMD-Be-12-Assumed) 53 – 1.0000 (SRM KN-5-2) 54 – 1.0000 (SRM KN-5-2-Assumed) 55 – 1.0000 (STD-11) 56 – 1.0000 (STD-11-Assumed) 57 – 0.9124 (NIST_30500) 58 – 0.9124 (NIST_30500-Assumed) or -9999 – for not applicable (NA)
BE10AP	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	377.90	Published Be-10 exposure age
BE10AP_ERR	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	22.10	Published Be-10 exposure age uncertainty

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
	[kyr]	or -9999 – for no data		
AL26AP_ERR	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value]</i> or -9999 – for no data	23.1	Published Al-26 exposure age uncertainty
Exposure age calculations using Be-10				
ABE_YR	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	372.241	Recalculated zero erosion Be-10 exposure age
ABE_ERREXT	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	30.065	External uncertainty for “ABE_YR” *
ABE_ERRINT	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	19.811	Internal uncertainty for “ABE_YR” *
Exposure age calculations using Al-26				
AAL_YR	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	331.959	Recalculated zero erosion Al-26 exposure age
AAL_ERREXT	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	32.567	External uncertainty for “AAL_YR” *
AAL_ERRINT	numeric [kyr]	<i>[value; two decimal places]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	19.312	Internal uncertainty for “AAL_YR” * * For detailed information see Balco et al. 2008 (10.1016/j.quageo.2007.12.001).

Table S8

Database field descriptions: FosSahul

OCTOPUSdata/ FosSahul collection. Database Index

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
Sample information				
OBSID1	text:I:U:NN	[FOS#####]	FOS00598	Unique sample identifier provided as part of the compilation. Serves as back reference to parent FosSahul fork (https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0267-3), with the prefix 'FOS' and wildcard zero(s) added to the original ID.
OBSID2	text	[value] or ND – no data	TEC-F	Original sample identifier (as published). This is NOT the laboratory code provided by some labs, but the ID used by authors of the source publication to identify the sample. Samples labelled only by numbers in the literature (e.g., 1, 2, 3 etc) have had a compound prefix – first three author name letters AND double-digit publication year – added (e.g. 'Nan87_1' for sample 1 (Nanson 1987)).
LABID	text	[value] or ND – no data	ND	Unique lab code assigned by the lab where age was determined. For radiocarbon (and for many luminescence) labs, the first part of the lab code refers to the determining facility.
LAB_FACLT	text:P	[value]	NA	Name of the laboratory where age was determined (where deducible from "LABID")
IGSNID	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Placeholder for <i>International Geo Sample Number</i> unique ID
Version of the database				
DBDOI	text	[value]	no_DOI_available	Digital object identifier (DOI) of OCTOPUSdata (sub-)collection
DBVERNO	numeric(7,3)	[value]	2.0	OCTOPUS database version number (major.minor)
Sample, site information and source of data				
SMPID	text:NN	[FOSMP#####x]	FOSMP00098a	Unique sample identifier that, first and foremost, serves database operation. FosSahul SMPIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated "X_WGS84" AND "Y_WGS84" AND "SITENAME" AND "OBSID2".

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
SITEID	text:NN	[FOSTE####x]	FOSTE0034a	Unique site identifier that, first and foremost, serves database operation. FosSahul SITEIDs have been aggregated using similarities in concatenated rounded (0) "X_WGS84" AND rounded (0) "Y_WGS84" AND "SITENAME".
METASITEID	text	[META_FOS####]	META_FOS0438	Unique metasite identifier that, first and foremost, serves database operation. FosSahul METASITEIDs have been aggregated for any site with n>25 observations.
METANAME	text	[value]	Tight Entrance Cave	Metasite name
METHODABBR	text:P:NN	[methodid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Amino Acid Racemization (AAR) 2 – Radiocarbon Dating (C14) 3 – Cation Ratio Dating (CRD) 4 – Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)	C14 5 – Oxidisable Carbon Ratio (OCR) 6 – Optically Stimulated Lum. (OSL) 7 – Thermoluminescence (TL) 8 – Uranium-Series (U)	Abbreviated type of method used in age determination 9 – Closed-system U-Series and ESR model (CSU-ESR) 10 – Stratigraphic correlation (Strat) 11 – Coupled U-ESR model (U-ESR)
FOS_MTDSUB	text:P	[fos_mtdsid – value (abbreviation)] 1 – Accelerator Mass Spectroscopy (AMS) 2 – C13 adjusted (C13_adj) 3 – Early uptake ESR (EU) 4 – Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) 5 – Linear uptake ESR (LU) 6 – Multicollector ICP-MS (MC-ICP-MS)	Multicollector ICP-MS 7 – Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry (TIMS) 8 – Thermally-transferred (TT)	Method specification if applicable. If 'NA' for 'C14' (in "FOS_MTD"), then 'C14' = beta-counting C14. 'C13_adj' along with radiocarbon dating has a -25 ‰ VPBD (Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite) correction and SC = stepped combustion. 'ICP-MS' and 'TIMS' along with U-series Th/U=laser-ablation. Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry and Thermal Ionization Mass Spectrometry, respectively. or -9991 – NA (NA); for not applicable -9999 – ND (ND); for no data
CNTRY	varchar(3):P	[value] or ND – no data	AUS	ISO 3166 Alpha-3 country code: https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search
REGION_INT	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Region where the study site is located
REGION_REG	varchar(3):P	AUS – Australia (without TSI) IDN – Indonesia	AUS	Refers to Sahul region. Same as "CNTRY" but needed to accommodate for 'TSI'

23.11.2022. DBVER 2021. Data type: numeric(precision, scale), for non-numeric: (3) = field length; I = indexed, U = unique, NN = not nullable, P = predefined.

Data type description <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/13/datatype.html>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		PNG – Papua New Guinea (without TSI) TLS – Timor-Leste	TSI – Torres Strait Islands	or ND – no data
DIV_ADMIN	varchar(7):P	AU-NSW – New South Wales AU-QLD – Queensland AU-SA – South Australia AU-TAS – Tasmania AU-VIC – Victoria AU-WA – Western Australia AU-ACT – Australian Capital Territory AU-NT – Northern Territory ID-JW – Jawa ID-KA – Kalimantan ID-ML – Maluku ID-NU – Nusa Tenggara ID-PP – Papua ID-SL – Sulawesi ID-SM – Sumatera PG-NCD – National Capital District (Port Moresby) PG-CPM – Central PG-CPK – Chimbu	AU-WA PG-EHG – Eastern Highlands PG-EBR – East New Britain PG-ESW – East Sepik PG-EPW – Enga PG-GPK – Gulf PG-HLA – Hela PG-JWK – Jiwaka PG-MPM – Madang PG-MRL – Manus PG-MBA – Milne Bay PG-MPL – Morobe PG-NIK – New Ireland PG-NPP – Northern PG-SAN – West Sepik PG-SHM – Southern Highlands PG-WPD – Western PG-WHM – Western Highlands PG-WBK – West New Britain	ISO 3166 code of the administrative region where the study site is located PG-NSB – Bougainville TL-AL – Aileu TL-AN – Ainaro TL-BA – Baucau TL-BO – Bobonaro TL-CO – Cova Lima TL-DI – Dili TL-ER – Ermera TL-LA – Lautém TL-LI – Liquiçá TL-MT – Manatuto TL-MF – Manufahi TL-OE – Oe-Cusse Ambeno TL-VI – Viqueque or ND – no data
DIV_OTHER	text:P	PG-Highlands – Highlands Region PG-Islands – Islands Region PG-Momase – Momase Region PG-Southern – Southern Region TSI-TWI – Top Western Islands TSI-NWI – Near Western Islands	NA TSI-INI – Inner Islands TSI-CI – Central Islands TSI-EI – Eastern Islands	Geographical region in ‘PNG’ and ‘TSI’ where study site is located or ND – no data NA – for not applicable
ISL_NAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Name of island where study site is located
LAKE	text	[value]	NA	Name of lake where study site is located

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or ND – no data NA – for not applicable		
BASIN	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Busselton Coast	Name of river basin where study site is located
AHGFL1	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	SWC	Geofabric AHGF river region code. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
AHGFL2	varchar(6):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	SWC_10	Geofabric AHGF combined river region code (“AHGLF1”) and topographic drainage division two-digit number. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
RIVNAME	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Busselton Coast	Geofabric AHGF river name. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of AHGF river names and codes is available at: http://www.bom.gov.au/metadata/catalogue/19115/ANZCWO503900426
RIVDIV	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	South West Coast	Geofabric AHGF river division name. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRACODE	varchar(3):P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	WAR	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia</i>
IBRAREGION	text:P	[value] or NA – for regions outside Australia	Warren	The location of the site within the relevant bioregion as defined by the Interim Bio-Regionalisation of Australia (IBRA7) framework. <i>Only used for data from Australia.</i> A full list of IBRA region names and codes is available at: https://www.awe.gov.au/agriculture-land/land/nrs/science/ibra/ibra7-codes
X_WGS84	numeric(10,6):NN	[value; six decimal places]	150.901171	WGS84 longitude of site <i>Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed.</i>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
	[decimal deg]	or -9999.99 – no data		Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.
Y_WGS84	numeric(10,6) :NN [decimal deg]	[value; six decimal places] or -9999.99 – no data	-34.414173	WGS84 latitude of site Culturally sensitive. Coordinates not to be displayed. Site coordinates randomly obfuscated within 25-km radius.
CORDS_ELEV	varchar(9):P	INTP – Coordinates interpolated from a published map or description ORIG – Originally published coordinates or ND – no data	ND_ND	Dual field. First part of value refers to source of coordinates (“X_WGS84”, “Y_WGS84”) for the sample site (‘INTP_’, or ‘ORIG_’, or ‘ND_’). Second part of value refers to “ELEVATION” (‘_INTP’, or ‘_ORIG’, or ‘_ND’). Nine (9) combinations possible
ELEVATION	numeric(6,2) [m]	[value, two decimal places] or -9999 – no data	-9999.99	Elevation above sea level of the sample
SITENAME	text	[value] or ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Tight Entrance Cave	Name of the site
SITE_SPEC	text	[value] or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Further specifies information given in “SITENAME”
ALTNAME1	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	ND	First alternative or additional name of the site (e.g., published under previous name etc.)
SITE_COMMT	text	[value] or NA – for not applicable	NA	Free text site comment field.
Reference information				
REFDBID1	text:NN	[value]	Prideaux:2010extinctions	Unique OCTOPUSdata reference identifier

23.11.2022. DBVER 2021. Data type: numeric(precision, scale), for non-numeric: (3) = field length; I = indexed, U = unique, NN = not nullable, P = predefined.

Data type description <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/13/datatype.html>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		<i>or</i> <i>ND – no data</i>		
OAID1	varchar(11):NN	<i>[value]</i> <i>or</i> <i>ND – no data</i>	OAID-000365	Unique OCTOPUSdata author identifier
AUTHOR1	text	<i>[value]</i> <i>or</i> ND – no data NA – for not applicable	Prideaux	Surname of the first author of the ORIGINAL DATA SOURCE publication/thesis author
PUBYEAR1	int2	<i>[YYYY] – Year</i> <i>or</i> 0 – for data not published -9999 – no data	2010	Year of the publication
REFID1	text	<i>[Abbrev_Publ_Name_Vol]</i> <i>or</i> Book Book_Chapter PhD_Thesis MSc_Thesis Hons_Thesis	P_Natl_Acad_Sci_USA_107 <i>or</i> second example Geol_Soc_Am_Bull_130 Not_Published Report_Published Report_Unpublished	Abbreviated name of journal and volume number, or type of publication (i.e. PhD thesis, Master thesis etc). Journal abbreviations according to https://images.webofknowledge.com/images/help/WOS/A_abrvjt.html Pers_Comm <i>or</i> ND – no data
REFDOI1	text	<i>[value] – where available</i> <i>or</i> ND – no data NA – for not applicable	10.1073/pnas.1011073107	Digital object identifier (DOI) where available. Where DOI unavailable, a preferably stable URL (preferentially National Library of Australia Trove, CNRI Handle System or JSTOR stable) has been captured as part of OCTOPUSdata reference database.
REFDBID2	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID2	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR2	text	<i>[value]</i> <i>or</i>	<i>NULL</i>	Surname of the first author of a selected GENERAL field site PUBLICATION/thesis author

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
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		<i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR2	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID2	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI2	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID3	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID3	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR3	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR3	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID3	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI3	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDBID4	text	Refer to REFDBID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
OAID4	varchar(11)	Refer to OAID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
AUTHOR4	text	Refer to AUTH2 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
PUBYEAR4	int2	Refer to PUBYEAR1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFID4	text	Refer to REFID1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		
REFDOI4	text	Refer to REFDOI1 field above for eligible <i>Values, Examples</i> and <i>Description</i> . <i>NULL</i> – for not applicable		

Sample characteristics

FOSMAT1	text:P	<i>[[fosmat1id – value (abbreviation)]]</i>	Sed	Type of dated remain
		1 – Bone (Bone) 2 – Bulk bone (Bone_bulk) 3 – Multiple bones (Bone_mult) 4 – Calcite filling in bone (Calc_bone) 5 – Calcite straw (reworked in bone breccia) (Calc_straw) 6 – Calcite within tooth (Calc_tooth) 7 – Carcass remains (Carcass) 8 – Calcite cement (Cement) 9 – Charcoal (Charcoal)	13 – Fish otolith (Fish_olth) 14 – Flowstone (Flow) 15 – Flowstone (oldest) (Flow_old) 16 – Flowstone straw (Flow_straw) 17 – Flowstone (youngest) (Flow_young) 18 – Gut content (Gut) 19 – Sarcophilus hair (Hair_sarco) 20 – Midden (Midden) 21 – Carbonate nodule (Nodule)	25 – Shell (Shell) 26 – Marine shell (Shell_mare) 27 – Skull (Skull) 28 – Skull (dentary) (Skull_dnty) 29 – Skull (maxilla) (Skull_max) 30 – Snail shell (Snail) 31 – Speleothem (Speleo) 32 – Coralline speleothem (Speleo_coral) 33 – Tooth (Tooth) 34 – Wood (Wood)

23.11.2022. DBVER 2021. Data type: numeric(precision, scale), for non-numeric: (3) = field length; I = indexed, U = unique, NN = not nullable, P = predefined.

Data type description <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/13/datatype.html>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		10 – Diprotodon crop content (Dipto_crop) 11 – Eggshell (Eggshell) 12 – Fireplace (Fireplace)	22 – Plant remains (Plant) 23 – Post-depositional formation (Post-deposit) 24 – Sediment (Sed)	35 – for other (Other) or -9991 – not applicable (NA) -9999 – no data (ND)
FOSMAT2	text:P	<i>[fosmat2id – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Apatite (Apatite) 2 – Bone (Bone) 3 – Multiple bones (Bone_mult) 4 – Burnt bone (Bone_burnt) 5 – Calcite (Calcite) 6 – Carbonate (Carb) 7 – Charcoal (Charcoal) 8 – Cellulose (Cellulose) 9 – Collagen (Collagen) 10 – Dentine (Dentine) 11 – Dentine/Enamel (Dentine/Enamel) 12 – Eggshell (Eggshell) 13 – Enamel (Enamel) 14 – Flesh (Flesh) 15 – Gelatine extract (Gelatine_extr) 16 – Gelatine fraction (Gelatine_frac) 17 – Hair (Hair) 18 – Acid and alkali insoluble residue (Insoble)	Calcite 19 – Acid insoluble fraction (Insoble_acid_frac) 20 – Acid insoluble residue (Insoble_acid_res) 21 – Molar (Molar) 22 – Organic band (Organic_layer) 23 – Organic carbon residue (Organic_carb) 24 – Organic fraction (Organic_frac) 25 – Organic material (Organic_mat) 26 – Otolith (Otolith) 27 – Peat (Peat) 28 – Carbonaceous pellet (Pellet_carb) 29 – Leaf, seed, stem fragments (Plant) 30 – Quartz (Quartz) 31 – Celtis seed (Seed_celtis) 32 – Shell (Shell) 33 – Shell (Vesunio ambiguous) (Shell_veles)	Type of dated material 34 – Bulk soil organics (Soil) 35 – Marine shell (Shell_mare) 36 – Speleothem (Speleo) 37 – Straw stalactite (Stalactite) 38 – Tooth (Tooth) 39 – Tooth from breccia (Tooth_breccia) 40 – Wood (Wood) 41 – Burnt wood (Wood_burnt) 42 – Carbonised wood (Wood_carb) 43 – for other (Other) 44 – Charcoal (assumed) (Charcoal?) 45 – Sediment (Sed) or -9991 – not applicable (NA) -9999 – no data (ND)
STRAT_TAPH	text:p	Strat – Stratigraphy available Taph – Taphonomy available Both – Strat AND Taph available Info – Other related information <i>Optional + REFDOI2, 3, and/ or 4 where applicable</i>	Strat or second example Both, REFDOI2, REFDOI3 or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	Whether stratigraphic (“Strat”), taphonomic (“Taph”) or even both (“Both”) information are available in source publication. “REFDOI” references link to secondary literature containing “STRAT_TAPH” information, so for example ‘Strat, REFDOI2’ would link to secondary stratigraphy linked to “REFDBID2”.
SPEC_ABUND	text:p	No – Species abundances unavailable Yes – Species abundances available	Yes, SupplMat or second example	Whether relative species abundances are given in source publication

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		<p>Yes, SupplMat – Species abundances available in Supplementary Material of original Publication</p> <p><i>Optional</i> + REFDO12, 3, and/ or 4 where applicable</p>	<p>Both, REFDO12, REFDO13</p> <p>or</p> <p>ND – for no data</p> <p>NA – for not applicable</p>	
SQUARE_XU	text	<p>[value]</p> <p>or</p> <p>ND – for no data</p> <p>Abbreviations used:</p> <p>AHD – Australian Height Datum, abv. – above, analyt. – analytical, arch. – archaeological, bel. – below, brec. – breccia, catal. – catalogue, class. – classic, cult. – cultural, dat. – datum, dep. – deposit, excav. – excavated/ -ion, geom. – geomorphological, hozn. – horizon, in. – inch(es), lay. – layer, low. – lower, meas. – measured, mega. – megafauna(l), no. – number, pleist. – Pleistocene, overl. – overlying, rel. – relative, sect. – section, sed. – sediment/s, shelt. – shelter, sqre. – square, strat. – stratigraphic, strm. – stratum, surf. – surface, trch. – trench(es), underl. – underlying, u. – unit, up. – upper</p>	U. D	Square or trench designation and/ or excavation unit or spit designation from where the sample is from. Recurrent nomenclature abbreviated as described in 'Values' to the left; abbreviations are not upper/ lower case sensitive.
SMP_COMMT	text	<p>[value]</p> <p>or</p> <p>NA – for not applicable</p>	NA	Free text sample comment field.
Linnaean classification				
SPECIES	text:p	<p>[value]</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9991 – NA (for not applicable)</p> <p>-9999 – ND (for no data)</p>	hatcheri	Most updated species name
GENUS	text:p	<p>[value]</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9991 – NA (for not applicable)</p> <p>-9999 – ND (for no data)</p>	Borongaboodie	Most updated genus name
FAMILY	text:p	<p>[value]</p> <p>or</p> <p>-9991 – NA (for not applicable)</p> <p>-9999 – ND (for no data)</p>	Potoroidae	Most updated family name

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
ORDR	text:p	<i>[ordrid – value]</i> 1 – Accipitriformes 2 – Anseriformes 3 – Anura 4 – Artiodactyla 5 – Carnivora 6 – Charadriiformes 7 – Chiroptera 8 – Chiroptera (Microchiroptera) 9 – Ciconiiformes 10 – Columbiformes 11 – Crocodylia 12 – Dasyuromorphia	Diprotodontia 13 – Diprotodontia 14 – Falconiformes 15 – Galliformes 16 – Gruiformes 17 – Lagomorpha 18 – Monotremata 19 – Passeriformes 20 – Pelecaniformes 21 – Peramelemorphia 22 – Procellariiformes 23 – Psittaciformes 24 – Rodentia	Most updated order name 25 – Sirenia 26 – Sphenisciformes 27 – Squamata 28 – Strigiformes 29 – Struthiniformes 30 – Suliformes 31 – Testudines 32 – Turniciformes or -9991 – NA (for not applicable) -9999 – ND (for no data)
INFRACLASS	text:p	<i>[infraclaid – value]</i> 1 – Anapsida 2 – Archosauromorpha 3 – Eutheria 4 – Gnathostomata 5 – Holotheria	Marsupialia 6 – Lepidosauromorpha 7 – Lepidosauromorpha 8 – Marsupialia 9 – Neoaves 10 – Ornithoraces	Most updated infraclass name 11 – Prototheria or -9991 – NA (for not applicable) -9999 – ND (for no data)
CLASS	text:p	<i>[classid – value]</i> 1 – Amphibia 2 – Aves 3 – Mammalia	Mammalia 4 – Reptilia 5 – Sauropsida	Most updated class name or -9991 – NA (for not applicable) -9999 – ND (for no data)
STATUS	varchar(7):P	Extant – extant Extinct – extinct or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	Extinct	Most updated status
MEGAFAUNA	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	No	‘Yes’ if species weight > 44 kg, otherwise ‘No’

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
C14 method specific				
C14_CALIB	varchar(3):P	Yes – Calibrated No – Uncalibrated or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Whether the published radiocarbon age is calibrated or uncalibrated
PHYSCLEAN	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Was the sample physically cleaned? For example, was the surface removed from bone (= 'Yes'), were rootlets and sediment removed from charcoal (= 'Yes').
CONTAM	varchar(8):P	Likely – Contamination likely Possible – Contamination possible No – Not contaminated Yes – Indication for contamination or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Whether the study authors suggest a contaminant may have occurred
CHEMYPEAB	text:P	<i>[chemypeid – value (abbreviation)]</i> 1 – Acid-alkali-acid and decalcification (AAA_decal) 2 – ABA_BC technique (ABA-BC) 3 – Acid-base-oxidation stepped combustion (ABOx-SC) 4 – Acetic acid treatment (Acetic) 5 – Alkali wash (Alkali_wash) 6 – Etching (Etch) 7 – Filtration (Filtration) 8 – Gelatinisation (Gelatinisation)	NA 9 – Hydrochloric acid etching (HCl_etch) 10 – Hydrochloric acid wash (HCl_wash) 11 – Treatment with HCl and NaOH (HCl,NaOH) 12 – Leaching (Leach) 13 – Boiling in saturated NaCl solution (NaCl_boil)	Abbreviated type of chemical pretreatment given to the sample as described in original publication. There may be considerable variation within each pretreatment code. 14 – no treatment (No) 15 – not reported (Not_rep) 16 – Ultrafiltration (Ultra) 17 – Wash (Wash) 18 – for other treatment (see attachment) (Other) or -9991 – not applicable (NA) -9999 – no data (ND)
CHEMPREPAB	text:P	<i>[chemprepid – abbreviation]</i> 1 – ABA 2 – ABA (base soluble)	ABA	Abbreviated type of chemical pretreatment given to the sample. Methods capture the majority of methods applied in

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		3 – ABA and bleach 4 – ABA and bleach-SC 5 – ABA-SC 6 – ABOx 7 – ABOx-SC 8 – Acid 9 – Acid (to extract apatite) 10 – Acid or ABA gelatinisation-ultrafiltration 11 – Acid or ABA-gelatinisation 12 – Alpha cellulose 13 – Alpha cellulose-SC 14 – AOx 15 – AOx-SC 16 – CARDS 17 – CARDS + acid 18 – Hydroxyproline 19 – HyPy 20 – Plasma Oxidation 21 – Potassium permanganate (to extract oxalate) 22 – Stepped hydrolysis 23 – XAD 24 – AAA	25 – AAA/ABA 26 – AAA/ABA/Acid 27 – ABAu 28 – Bulk 29 – Coll_SC 30 – Coll_ultra 31 – Gelatin 32 – Longin	<p>Australia. There may be considerable variation within each pretreatment code.</p> <p>'ABA' (acid-base-acid) is equivalent to 'AAA' (acid-alkali-acid).</p> <p>'ABOx-SC' = acid-base-oxidation-stepped-combustion.</p> <p>'HyPy' = hydrogen pyrolysis.</p> <p>'Acid-gelatinisation' = the Longin method.</p> <p>'CARDS' = Carbonate Density Separation.</p> <p>'XAD' = resin used to clean amino acids. Note that 'XAD' flag overwrites potential other pretreatment.</p> <p>Plasma oxidation and potassium permanganate methods refer to methods which aim to convert a specific portion of the sample to CO₂ and may involve a variety of other steps.</p> <p>'Bulk' = Several fragments dated together, 'SC' = Stepped combustion, 'Ultra' = Ultrafiltration, 'Longin' = Modified Longin method, 'Gelatin' = Gelatinisation, 'Coll' = Collagen</p>
		18 – Hydroxyproline 19 – HyPy 20 – Plasma Oxidation 21 – Potassium permanganate (to extract oxalate) 22 – Stepped hydrolysis 23 – XAD 24 – AAA	25 – AAA/ABA 26 – AAA/ABA/Acid 27 – ABAu 28 – Bulk 29 – Coll_SC 30 – Coll_ultra 31 – Gelatin 32 – Longin	33 – No 34 – Ultra 99 – Other or -9991 – no applicable (NA) -9999 – no data (ND)
XTR_PROBLM	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Whether the study authors reported extraction problems
CN_RATIO	numeric	<i>[value]</i> or -9999.99 – for no data	-9999.99	Measured atomic C:N ratio of the pretreated sample
PCT_N	numeric [%]	<i>[value]</i> or	-9999.99	Measured %N of the pretreated sample

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		-9991.11 – for not reported -9999.99 – for no data		
C14_XRDIFF	varchar(3):P	No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	For corals/shells only: Indicates if X-ray diffraction shows that recrystallisation is insignificant
AAR method specific				
AAR_T_HIST	varchar(4):P	Fine or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Thermal history of the sample. Based on the established quality rating criteria (Rodríguez-Rey et al. 2015): is the thermal history of the sample unknown or were materials burnt (i.e., is “AAR_T_HIST” not ‘Fine’), then rating will be ‘C’.
AAR_CLOSD	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Whether the material has demonstrated closed-system behaviour
AAR_UNCERT	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Whether multiple analyses were replicated with low uncertainties
AAR_INCAL	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Whether reliable calibration was done using independent dating techniques
U_TH method specific				
U_TH_PRE	text:p	Grind_Etch – Grinding and acid etching or ND – for no data	ND	Short description of pretreatment

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		NA – for not applicable		
U_TH_CLOSD	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	ND	Uranium-series ages for teeth (dentine) and bone: whether closed-system behaviour has been demonstrated by U-series profiling and modelling based on continuous profiles or spot sampling using laser ablation
U_TH_DCORR	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	Yes	Uranium-series ages for closed-system of no body remains (e.g., speleothems, corals, calcite within bones etc): Whether a correction was made for detrital thorium contamination
ESR method specific				
ESR_I_DR10	text:P	<10 – Less than 10% >10 – Greater than 10% or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	ESR ages: Whether the internal dose rate is less/ greater 10%
ESR_GAMMA	text:P	In_situ Assumed or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	ESR ages: Whether the gamma dose rate was measured 'In_situ' or was 'Assumed'
Luminescence method specific				
ALIQ_TYPE	varchar(3):P	MA – Multi Aliquot SA – Single Aliquot SG – Single Grain or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Reported aliquot type used for equivalent dose determination
BLEACH_STS	text:P	Adequately – Adequately bleached Partially – Partially bleached	NA	Luminescence bleaching status.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
		or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable		Whether the sediment has been bleached ‘Adequately’ or ‘Partially’.
AGEMD_TRUE	varchar(3):P	Yes No or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	NA	Luminescence single grain equivalent dose model. Whether the luminescence age can be modelled
Age determination and quality				
AGE	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	112.00	Published age
AGE_ERR	numeric [ka]	[value; three decimal places] or -9999.99 – for no data	11.00	Published total age error
AGE_TYPE	varchar(5):P	Min – Minimum age Max – Maximum age Exact – Exact age or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	Exact	Temporal quality of published age estimate
AGE_CI	varchar(3):P	1SD – 1 standard deviation 2SD – 2 standard deviations or ND – for no data	1SD	Published confidence interval on the age estimate
AGE_PREQ	varchar(3):P	m* – Highest reliability m – High reliability B – Low reliability C – Lowest reliability or ND – for no data	m	Quality rating of dating protocol (see Rodríguez-Rey, M. et al. 2015. Quat Geochronol 30. Fig. 1.)

23.11.2022. DBVER 2021. Data type: numeric(precision, scale), for non-numeric: (3) = field length; I = indexed, U = unique, NN = not nullable, P = predefined.

Data type description <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/13/datatype.html>

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
AGE_Q	varchar(3):P	A* – Highly reliable A – Reliable B – Unreliable C – Highly unreliable or ND – for no data	A	Reliability rating of fossil age (see Rodríguez-Rey, M. et al. Quat Geochronol 30, 2015.)
AGE_SUBQ	varchar(6):P	a – Above w – Within b – Below or ND – for no data NA – for not applicable	Within	Sub-category of “AGE_Q”, if reliable by association (see Rodríguez-Rey, M. et al. Quat Geochronol 30, 2015.)
AGE_ASSOC1	varchar(8):P	Direct Indirect or ND – for no data	Indirect	‘Direct’ age estimates have been derived from vertebrate parts of the target species itself. ‘Indirect’ ages are not based on target species body parts, but still can be used based on association, i.e., the relationship between the target fossil and the dated structure/ material.
AGE_ASSOC2	text:P	Yes – Clear association No – Association not clear Uncertain – Association uncertain NA – for AGE_ASSOC1 = ‘Direct’ or ND – for no data	Yes	Applicable if “AGE_ASSOC1” = ‘Indirect’. Additional descriptor for the quality of the association between the dated structure/ material and the target specimen. Is NA if “AGE_ASSOC1” = ‘Direct’.
AGE_PREQ_R	text	[value] or ND – for no data	All requirements met	Reason for “AGE_PREQ” value
AGE_Q_R	text	[value] or ND – for no data	Indirect age	Reason for “AGE_Q” value
AGE_COMMT	text	[Comment] or	UMA01789 Sep-2007	Free text age comment field.

Field Name	Type & Units	Values	Example	Description
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		NA – for not applicable		
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